

Hypothetical complete extraction: a new approach

A comparative analysis

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Abstract

This paper proposes and substantiates a generalisation of the regional extraction method used by Dietzenbacher et al. (1993). The production system represented by an input-output table is broken down into three flow matrices: input, final goods, and value added. The approach of Dietzenbacher et al. (1993) focuses on the input flow matrix to obtain both the backward and forward dependence. However, the present paper offers two alternative contributions within the theoretical framework: on the one hand, it looks at inclusion of the final demand flow matrix to calculate the backward dependence and, on the other hand, the inclusion of the value added matrix to calculate the forward dependence. These two approaches are then compared by applying them to a real-life case, using the EUREGIO database.

Key words: Interregional input-output model, hypothetical extraction method, backward linkages, forward linkages, EUREGIO.

Classification JEL: C67, D57, R15

1. Introduction

Quantifying the level of integration and intersectoral or interregional dependence of an economy is of great interest, both for researchers and public institutions. The input-output tables are an ideal tool for identifying the origin and the regional and/or sectoral destination of trade flows. The hypothetical extraction method (HEM) enables the dependence between regions and/or sectors to be quantified and is an alternative to the classic multiplier analysis proposed by Leontief (1953). According to Dietzenbacher et al. (1993a), the HEM was developed by Strassert (1968) and applied, empirically, by Schultz (1977) to determine the key sectors of an economy. Originally, the method was aimed at quantifying sectoral dependence in uniregional models but has since become one of the most used methods to measure intersectoral relationships and the importance of sectors in the economy (Dietzenbacher et al., 2019). With the development of multiregional models (Round, 1978; Jensen et al., 1979; Sawyer and Miller, 1983; Hewings, 1985; Brucker et al., 1987; Lahr, 1993), Dietzenbacher et al. (1993a) presented an extension of the HEM to identify interregional dependence.

The HEM quantifies the interrelation of a region or a sector in a production system, measuring the effect generated by its hypothetical extraction. Taking an interregional or intersectoral input-output matrix as a reference, the HEM consists of extracting a region or sector from this matrix to determine the effect of the extraction on the production activity of the other regions or sectors. Methodologically, the HEM quantifies the difference between the total production of the economic system in the original situation and the production of the economic system in the hypothetical situation, that is, when the extraction of a region or a sector is simulated. The aforementioned incidence makes it possible to determine the backward linkage or the forward linkage of the extracted region or sector, depending on whether the model used is the Leontief demand-driven model or, alternatively, the Ghosh supply-driven model.

The originality of the proposal by Dietzenbacher et al. (1993a), through a regional HEM, essentially consists of quantifying interregional links from a multiregional input-output table. To do this, a region is extracted from the input flow matrix and the variation that this extraction generates in the total production of each of the economic units that make up the economic system is quantified. This impact is the backward dependence of the region. Similarly, in the supply model, the extraction of a region from the input flow matrix leads to a reduction in the system's production and this gives the forward dependence.

The objective of this study is to extend and generalise the approach proposed by Dietzenbacher et al. (1993a) so that the results and the analyses derived are more in line with what would happen in the economy when hypothetically extracting, as proposed by the HEM, a region of the production system. It can be assumed that when a region is extracted, in addition to the input flow matrix, the final demand matrix and the value added matrix will also be affected. Therefore, the hypothetical extraction of a region from the production system will affect all the flow matrices of the input-output table, not just one of them as proposed by Dietzenbacher et al. (1993a).

The extraction in a region of only the input flow matrix, as discussed by Dietzenbacher et al. (1993a), can be considered a *partial extraction*. The joint extraction of the input

flow and final demand matrices implies a *complete extraction* on the demand side. The joint extraction of the input flow and value added matrices would be a *complete extraction* on the supply side. The contribution of this study is to include the final demand matrix in the regional HEM when the extraction is analysed on the demand side, and to consider the value added matrix when the extraction is carried out on the supply side.

This paper presents the analytical processes that enable the impact of the partial and complete extraction of a region to be quantified. Both approaches are then compared through an empirical exercise which uses data from the EUREGIO database. Specifically, the input-output table from 2009 is used, which allows each of the 17 Spanish Autonomous Communities (CCAA) to be individually extracted. The results obtained using the approach proposed by Dietzenbacher et al. (1993a) and the one proposed by this study can then be compared.

The paper is set out as follows. After the Introduction, section 2 presents the technical background. In section 3, application of the HEM in both approaches is explained and developed. Section 4 shows the empirical application of the proposed approaches of the regional HEM to the Spanish regions. Lastly, section 5 presents the conclusions of the study. The paper is accompanied by Reference list and three Annexes.

2. Technical background

In general, a production system represented by an input-output table is made up of three flow matrices: input matrix, final demand matrix and value added matrix. These matrices are Z , F and VA in Table 1. In addition, the production vector is denoted as X , where X' is the transposed vector of X .

In general, models inspired by input-output tables, and particularly the Leontief demand model, allow us to analyse the consequences that an alteration in final demand has on the production system. Thus, in Leontief's model (1953, 1974), the leading role is assumed by the economic agents who make demand decisions, with equilibrium production of the original situation being determined by equation (1):

$$(1) \quad X = (I - A)^{-1}f = Lf$$

where: X is the column vector of the actual gross production in a position of equilibrium, f is the column vector of the demand for final goods¹, A is the technical coefficients

¹ The column vector f is given by: $f = F e = \begin{pmatrix} f_{11} & \cdots & f_{1m} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ f_{n1} & \cdots & f_{nm} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} f_1 \\ \vdots \\ f_n \end{pmatrix}$, e being a column vector of adequate dimension of unitary values and F is the final demand matrix of m sectors.

matrix², $L = (I - A)^{-1}$ is the total requirements matrix or Leontief matrix, and I is the adequate dimension identity matrix.

Table 1. Input-output table

Input flow matrix Z	Final demand flow matrix F	Production vector X
Value added matrix VA		
Production vector X'		

Note: Z is the square input matrix
 F is the final demand matrix
 VA is the value-added matrix
 X is the column vector of total production.

Source: Compiled by the authors

When a region is extracted, its demand is reduced and, in turn, the regions that supply goods to it also reduce demand. So, an interactive process is set in motion that leads to a general decrease in the production of the economic system. This incidence is what is called backward dependence or pull effect.

Similarly, in Ghosh's (1958, 1968) supply model, it is the economic agents who decide the levels of production. In the Ghosh model, the equilibrium production in the original situation is determined by the equation (2):

$$(2) \quad X' = v(I - B)^{-1} = vG$$

² The technical coefficients a_{ij} are obtained as the quotient between the sales of Region i to Region j and the production of the buyer region j , X_j . Thus, $a_{ij} = \frac{z_{ij}}{X_j}$ and $A = Z \hat{X}^{-1}$ where \hat{X}^{-1} is the inverse of the diagonal matrix of total production.

where: X' is a row vector of actual gross production, v is the row vector of the gross value added³, B is the coefficients of distribution matrix⁴ and $G = (1 - B)^{-1}$ is the Ghosh matrix.

If a region reduces its supply of goods, it will affect the linked regions, which in turn decrease production. Once again, an interactive process starts, like that of the Leontief model, which leads to a reduction in the level of production of the economic system. This contraction in production makes it possible to quantify the forward dependence or push effect of the region.

The regional HEM measures the dependence of a region assuming that, hypothetically, it is extracted from the production system. The difference in production, with and without this region, quantifies its dependence. Within the framework of an input-output table, the HEM consists of excluding the elements corresponding to the commercial exchanges of a region with the other regions and determining the incidence of this extraction in the production activity. In order to illustrate the HEM, an input-output table of 21 regions is presented, as shown in Table 2.

The application of the HEM involves partitioning the matrices described in Table 2. Table 3 shows a schema of the input-output matrix partitioned and adapted to the HEM that allows the effect of extracting Region 1 to be quantified. Henderson and Searle (1981) and Miller and Lahr (2001) perform an exhaustive analysis of the calculation with partitioned matrices. The input matrix Z , which is a 21x21 square matrix, can be partitioned into four sub-matrices, where Z^{11} is a 1x1 matrix, Z^{1R} is a 1x20 row vector, Z^{R1} is a 20x1 column vector and Z^{RR} is a 20x20 matrix (see Table 2 and Table 3). In a similar way, the final demand matrices, the input matrix or value added matrix and the production vector can also be partitioned⁵ (see Table 3).

³ The row vector v is given by: $v = e' VA = (1 \quad \dots \quad 1) \begin{pmatrix} v_{11} & \dots & v_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ v_{c1} & \dots & v_{cn} \end{pmatrix}$. VA is the value added matrix of components c .

⁴ The coefficients of distribution b_{ij} are given as the coefficient between the purchases of Region j from Region i and the production of the supplier region i , X_i . Thus, $b_{ij} = \frac{z_{ij}}{x_i}$.

⁵ In a similar way, following Miller and Lahr (2001), the matrix of technical coefficients can be partitioned $A = \begin{bmatrix} A^{11} & A^{1R} \\ A^{R1} & A^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$ and the distribution matrix $B = \begin{bmatrix} B^{11} & B^{1R} \\ B^{R1} & B^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$.

Table 2. Input-output matrix of 21 regions

			Input flow matrix			Final demand matrix			Produc-tion
			(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
			R_1	(R_j)	R_{21}	R_1	(R_j)	R_{21}	X
Input flow matrix	(a)	R_1	$z_{1,1}$	$z_{1,j}$	$z_{1,21}$	$f_{1,1}$	$f_{1,j}$	$f_{1,21}$	X_1
	(b)	(R_i)	$z_{i,1}$	$z_{i,j}$	$z_{i,21}$	$f_{i,1}$	$f_{i,j}$	$f_{i,21}$	X_i
	(c)	R_{21}	$z_{21,1}$	$z_{21,j}$	$z_{21,21}$	$f_{21,1}$	$f_{21,j}$	$f_{21,21}$	X_{21}
Value Added	Vector	(d)	v	v_1	v_j	v_{21}			
		(e)	v^1	v_1^1	v_j^1	v_{21}^1			
	Matrix	(f)	(v^i)	v_1^i	v_j^i	v_{21}^i			
		(g)	v^{21}	v_1^{21}	v_j^{21}	v_{21}^{21}			
Produc-tion	(h)	X'	X_1	X_j	X_{21}				

Note 1: The shaded cells indicate the elements that correspond to the transactions of Region 1 with the other regions.

Note 2: The subscripts refer to Region i of origin and Region j of destination. Thus: z_{ij} are inputs produced by Region i and demanded by Region j. $f_{i,j}$ are the final goods produced by Region i and demanded by Region j. X_i is the total production of Region i. v_j^i is the value added generated in Region j due to the production delivered by Region i. v_j is the aggregate value added generated by Region j and v is the row vector of the aggregate total value added.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Table 3. Partitioned input-output matrix for Region 1

$\begin{bmatrix} Z^{11} & Z^{1R} \\ Z^{R1} & Z^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} f^{11} & f^{1R} \\ f^{R1} & f^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} X^1 \\ X^R \end{bmatrix}$
$\begin{bmatrix} v^{11} & v^{1R} \\ v^{R1} & v^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$		
$\begin{bmatrix} X^{1'} & X^{R'} \end{bmatrix}$		

Note: The sum, by row, of the elements of the final demand matrix provides the column vector $\begin{bmatrix} f^1 \\ f^R \end{bmatrix}$, while the sum, by columns, of the elements of the matrix of value added gives the row vector: $\begin{bmatrix} v^1 & v^R \end{bmatrix}$.

Source: Compiled by the authors based on Table 2.

3. Hypothetical extraction method

The HEM enables the backward and forward dependencies of the regions to be calculated. Backward linkages or the pull effect of a region is understood as the inputs required from other regions to generate its production, according to the Leontief model, whereas, following the Ghosh model, forward linkages or the push effect is the dependence of a region on the input requirements of other regions. Therefore, in the backward effect, the dependent region buys the inputs it needs from other regions, and in the forward effect, the dependent region sells the inputs that other regions require.

3.1 HEM: backward dependence

By extracting a region from the production system, the impact of its extraction can be analysed, on the demand side, through different transmission mechanisms that refer to both the input flow matrix and the final demand flow matrix. For clarity of presentation, Region 1 is the region being extracted.

Input flow matrix

The mechanism of transmission, via demand, of inputs to other regions affects the goods that appear in the column of the region in the intermediate goods matrix (see column (1) of Table 2). When a region is extracted, the internal inputs ($Z^{11} = z_{11}$) are maintained, while the external inputs are cancelled, which means that in Table 3, $Z^{R1} = [0]$. It can be concluded that, if the demand for external inputs is modified, the external level of production will be altered, and in turn this will modify the acquisition of inputs produced in Region 1.

In the case of the mechanism of transmission, via supply, of inputs to other regions, these flows of goods appear in the row of the region in the input matrix (see row (a) of Table

2). When Region 1 is extracted, the sales of inputs to other regions are cancelled, $Z^{1R} = [0]$ in Table 3, while the internal sales are maintained (Z^{11}). It can be affirmed that, if the sales of inputs to other regions are modified, the production activity of Region 1 is altered and, consequently, the purchase of inputs by other regions is also modified.

Final demand flow matrix

The transmission mechanism via final demand affects the flow of goods that appears in the column for the region in the final demand matrix (see column (4) of Table 2). It should be noted that when Region 1 is extracted, the flow of external final demand is cancelled, $f^{R1} = [0]$ in Table 3, while the internal final demand is maintained (f^{11}). If the external final demand is modified, external production activity will be affected. The other regions in turn will alter their demand for inputs, meaning the production activity-of Region 1 will also be affected.

Lastly, in the transmission mechanism via supply, the flow of affected goods is shown in the row of the region in the final demand matrix (see row (a) of Table 2). When a region is extracted its sales to other regions are cancelled, in Table 3 this is equivalent to $f^{1R} = [0]$, while their internal sales are maintained (f^{11}). Consequently, if sales are modified, purchases of external inputs are altered which will affect the external economic activity.

Table 4. Matrix diagram of the transmission mechanisms of the input flow and final demand matrices, via supply and demand, under different scenarios

		Input matrix $Z = [z_{ij}]$			
		Extraction of purchases and sales			
		No		Yes	
Final demand matrix $F = [f_{ij}]$	Extraction of purchases and sales	No	$\begin{bmatrix} Z^{11} & Z^{1R} \\ Z^{R1} & Z^{RR} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f^{11} & f^{1R} \\ f^{R1} & f^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$	Yes	$\begin{bmatrix} Z^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & Z^{RR} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f^{11} & f^{1R} \\ f^{R1} & f^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$
	Yes	$\begin{bmatrix} Z^{11} & Z^{1R} \\ Z^{R1} & Z^{RR} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & f^{R1} \end{bmatrix}$	Yes	$\begin{bmatrix} Z^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & Z^{RR} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & f^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$	

Source: Compiled by the authors.

As such, when a region of the production system is extracted, this extraction can be carried out partially, blocking only some of the transmission mechanisms, or completely, blocking all transmission mechanisms. Miller and Lahr (2001) examine all possible extractions of the input matrix⁶. However, they do not consider the possible extraction of final demand. This study finds that the more flow matrices the extraction affects, the

⁶ Miller and Lahr (2001) find that several alternative extractions produce identical rankings of sectors.

lower the level of production reached and, consequently, the greater the pull effect or dependence effect. This increase in the pull effect is general, but there is no proportionality between the result and the flow matrices considered in the extraction. In summary, Table 4 shows how the model matrices are affected according to different scenarios.

Leontief demand model: Extraction of the input flow matrix.

As mentioned above, extraction of the region taking into account only the input flow matrix is considered as partial extraction.

The quantification of the impact of the extraction is carried out through the difference between the level of production reached, under the assumption that there is no exchange of input flow between the extracted region and the other regions, and the level of equilibrium production of the economic system in the original situation. Without loss of generality, and for simplicity of presentation, Region 1 is denoted as the region being extracted.

From the Leontief model, the equilibrium production of the economic system is given, in the original situation, by equation (3), using the partitioned technical coefficients matrix:

$$(3) \quad X = [I - A]^{-1}f = \begin{bmatrix} I - A^{11} & -A^{1R} \\ -A^{R1} & I - A^{RR} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} f^1 \\ f^R \end{bmatrix}$$

with X being the column vector of the regional production before extraction, f^1 and f^R the final demands of Region 1 and the other regions, respectively, defined in Table 3. The superscripts 11 , $1R$, $R1$ and RR refer to the blocks in which the vectors and matrices are partitioned to separate the intra-regional and inter-regional flows of extracted Region 1.

In order to estimate the production after extraction of Region 1, \bar{X}_I^L , the elements of the row and column of the region to be extracted are set to zero in the regional technical coefficients matrix, except for the element of the main diagonal. The Leontief model is used to obtain the new level of production reached, with the same final demand vector of equation (3):

$$(4) \quad \bar{X}_I^L = \begin{bmatrix} I - A^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & I - A^{RR} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} f^1 \\ f^R \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (I - A^{11})^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & (I - A^{RR})^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f^1 \\ f^R \end{bmatrix}$$

The backward dependence of Region 1, which measures the impact of its extraction, is obtained from the difference between the production values achieved before and after extraction by subtracting equations (3) and (4).

$$(5) \quad X - \bar{X}_I^L = \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} I - A^{11} & -A^{1R} \\ -A^{R1} & I - A^{RR} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} - \begin{bmatrix} (I - A^{11})^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & (I - A^{RR})^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \right\} \begin{bmatrix} f^1 \\ f^R \end{bmatrix}$$

Equation (5) corresponds to the HEM proposed by Dietzenbacher et al. (1993a) and enables the partial economic effect attributable to the inputs after the hypothetical extraction of Region 1 to be calculated. Furthermore, this equation enables the dependence on Region 1 of each of the others to be determined, as well as of the set of Regions R.

Leontief demand model: Joint extraction of input flow and final demand matrices

In this case, it is assumed that extraction from the region jointly affects the input flow and final demand matrices, referred to as complete extraction. The production level of the economic system after extracting Region 1 is obtained using equation (6):

$$(6) \quad \bar{X}_{I+FD}^L = \begin{bmatrix} (I - A^{11})^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & (I - A^{RR})^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{f}^1 \\ \bar{f}^R \end{bmatrix}$$

The backward dependence with complete extraction of Region 1 is determined by equation (7), which is defined as the difference between equations (3) and (6):

$$(7) \quad X - \bar{X}_{I+FD}^L = \begin{bmatrix} I - A^{11} & -A^{1R} \\ -A^{R1} & I - A^{RR} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} f^1 \\ f^R \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} (I - A^{11})^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & (I - A^{RR})^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{f}^1 \\ \bar{f}^R \end{bmatrix}$$

Leontief demand model: Extraction of the final demand flow matrix

It is now assumed that extraction of the region affects only the final demand flow matrix, which implies partial extraction. In this case, the effect of extraction of Region 1, considering only the final demand matrix, is obtained as the difference between the complete extraction, see equation (7), and the partial extraction, see equation (5). This difference provides the value of the decrease in production attributable to the extraction of the final demand and reflects the backward effect of the extraction of Region 1 only from the final demand flow matrix.

This backward effect can also be calculated by subtracting the production achieved with partial extraction and with complete extraction, equations (4) and (6):

$$(8) \quad \bar{X}_I^L - \bar{X}_{I+FD}^L = \begin{bmatrix} (I - A^{11})^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & (I - A^{RR})^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \left(\begin{bmatrix} f^1 \\ f^R \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \bar{f}^1 \\ \bar{f}^R \end{bmatrix} \right)$$

Table 5 shows, schematically, the equilibrium production equation of the economic system in the original situation. The production equations after both partial and complete extractions are also presented.

In this study, when extracting a region, firstly, the partial extraction of the input flow matrix is considered and, secondly, the complete extraction of the input flow matrix and the final demand flow matrix, as presented in Table 5. These two extractions allow the impact of only the final demand of the extraction on production to be calculated, which also supposes, as has been commented, a partial extraction. Thus, the objective of this contribution is the comparison and extension of the HEM proposed by Dietzenbacher et al. (1993a) with complete extraction and partial extraction of final goods.

Table 5. Level of production according to the different scenarios considered

Matrix of technical coefficients	Matrix of final demand flow	Equation to estimate the level of production	Leontief model. Equilibrium production
$\begin{bmatrix} A^{11} & A^{1R} \\ A^{R1} & A^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} f^{11} & f^{1R} \\ f^{R1} & f^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$	$X = \begin{bmatrix} I - A^{11} & -A^{1R} \\ -A^{R1} & I - A^{RR} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} f^1 \\ f^R \end{bmatrix}$	Original situation
$\begin{bmatrix} A^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & A^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} f^{11} & f^{1R} \\ f^{R1} & f^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$	$\bar{X}_I^L = \begin{bmatrix} (I - A^{11})^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & (I - A^{RR})^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f^1 \\ f^R \end{bmatrix}$	Partial extraction (I) Dietzenbacher et al.(1993a)
$\begin{bmatrix} A^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & A^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} f^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & f^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$	$\bar{X}_{I+FD}^L = \begin{bmatrix} (I - A^{11})^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & (I - A^{RR})^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{f}^1 \\ \bar{f}^R \end{bmatrix}$	Complete extraction (I+FD)

Note: X measures the level of original equilibrium production; \bar{X}_I^L is the level of production in the input matrix after the extraction; \bar{X}_{I+FD}^L is the level of production in the input matrix and in the final demand matrix after joint extraction.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

3.2. HEM: forward dependence

Analysis of the HEM from the supply side, based on the Ghosh model, can be done through different transmission mechanisms, which refer to both the input flow matrix and the value added matrix.

Input flow matrix

The mechanism of transmission of external demand for inputs (from other regions) is reflected in the value of the goods that appear in column (1) of the matrix of intermediate goods (see Table 2). When a region is extracted it is assumed that internal inputs (Z^{11}) are maintained, while the external inputs are cancelled, which means that, in Table 3, $Z^{R1} = [0]$. It can be concluded that, if the external demand for inputs is modified, the external production activity will be altered, which in turn will modify the acquisition of the inputs produced by Region 1.

Regarding the transmission mechanism via the supply of inputs to other regions, these goods appear in row (a) in the input matrix (see Table 2). When a region is extracted, the sale of inputs to other regions are cancelled, and, in Table 3, $Z^{1R} = [0]$, while internal sales (Z^{11}) remain the same. Therefore, if the external sales of inputs are modified, the production activity of Region 1 is modified and, consequently, the external purchase of inputs is also affected

Value added matrix

If the matrix of primary income flows is affected, for Region 1 this affects column (1) of the value added matrix (see Table 2). It should be noted that, when a region is extracted, the value added generated by the region is cancelled $v^{R1} = [0]$, while the internal value added is maintained (v^{11}), see Table 3. In this way, if the value added is modified, the production of Region 1 is altered which, in turn, will affect external economic activity.

Regarding the transmission mechanism via induced value added⁷ (see Table 2), these values appear in row (e) of Region 1 in the value added matrix. When extracting a region the induced value added is cancelled, $v^{1R} = [0]$, (see Table 3), but the region's own sales remain the same (v^{11}). Consequently, if the induced value added is modified, the production of the other regions is altered and a process of interaction between regions begins, which affects the production of the economic system. In summary, Table 6 presents the different scenarios that can be considered.

Table 6. Matrix diagram of the transmission mechanisms of the input flow and value added matrices, via supply and demand, under different scenarios

		Input flow matrix $Z = [z_{ij}]$					
		Extraction of purchases and sales					
		No		Yes			
Values added matrix $V = [v_j^i]$.	Extraction of purchase and sales	No	$\begin{bmatrix} Z^{11} & Z^{1R} \\ Z^{R1} & Z^{RR} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v^{11} & v^{1R} \\ v^{R1} & v^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$		Yes	$\begin{bmatrix} Z^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & Z^{RR} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v^{11} & v^{1R} \\ v^{R1} & v^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$	
	Yes	$\begin{bmatrix} Z^{11} & Z^{1R} \\ Z^{R1} & Z^{RR} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & v^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$		Yes	$\begin{bmatrix} Z^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & Z^{RR} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & v^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$		

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Ghosh supply model: Extraction of the input flow matrix

Next, Region 1 is extracted from the input flow matrix. Using the Ghosh model, and partitioning the distribution matrix, the equilibrium production in the original situation, X' , is given by equation (9):

$$(9) \quad X' = [v^1 \ v^R] [I - B]^{-1} = [v^1 \ v^R] \begin{bmatrix} I - B^{11} & -B^{1R} \\ -B^{R1} & I - B^{RR} \end{bmatrix}^{-1}$$

⁷ A distinction is made between the value added that a region generates due to all its production activity and the value added that one region allows another to generate by demanding the goods that the latter produces. This value added is called induced value added.

with X' being the file vector of equilibrium production in the original situation before extracting Region 1, while v^1 and v^R are the value added vectors defined in Table 3.

In order to obtain production, $\bar{X}_I^{G'}$, after extracting Region 1, the elements of the row and column of Region 1 are set to zero in the distribution coefficient matrix, except for the element on the main diagonal. Using the Ghosh equation again and with the same row vector of value added as in equation (9), the equilibrium production vector after extraction is obtained from equation (10):

$$(10) \quad \bar{X}_I^{G'} = [v^1 \ v^R] \begin{bmatrix} I - B^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & I - B^{RR} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} = [v^1 \ v^R] \begin{bmatrix} (I - B^{11})^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & (I - B^{RR})^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$$

The forward dependence of Region 1, after its extraction from the input matrix, is obtained by subtracting equations (9) and (10):

$$(11) \quad X' - \bar{X}_I^{G'} = [v^1 \ v^R] \left(\begin{bmatrix} I - B^{11} & -B^{1R} \\ -B^{R1} & I - B^{RR} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} - \begin{bmatrix} I - B^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & I - B^{RR} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \right)$$

Equation (11) corresponds to the equation proposed by Dietzenbacher et al. (1993a) and allows the partial forward dependence of the hypothetical extraction of Region 1 from the input flow matrix to be quantified.

Ghosh supply model: Joint extraction of input flow and value added matrices

Next, the level of production reached in the economic system is obtained, $\bar{X}_{I+VA}^{G'}$, after joint extraction of Region 1 in the input flow and value added matrices through the following equation:

$$(12) \quad \bar{X}_{I+VA}^{G'} = [\bar{v}^1 \ \bar{v}^R] \begin{bmatrix} I - B^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & I - B^{RR} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} = [\bar{v}^1 \ \bar{v}^R] \begin{bmatrix} (I - B^{11})^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & (I - B^{RR})^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$$

where $[\bar{v}^1 \ \bar{v}^R]$ defines the row vector of value added after extraction of Region 1.

The complete forward dependence of Region 1 can be obtained by subtracting equations (9) and (12):

$$(13) \quad X' - \bar{X}_{I+VA}^{G'} = [v^1 \ v^R] \begin{bmatrix} I - B^{11} & -B^{1R} \\ -B^{R1} & I - B^{RR} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} - [\bar{v}^1 \ \bar{v}^R] \begin{bmatrix} I - B^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & I - B^{RR} \end{bmatrix}^{-1}$$

Ghosh supply model: Extraction of the value added flow matrix

The effect of extraction in Region 1 of only the value added flow matrix is obtained as the difference of the complete extraction, equation (13), and the partial extraction, equation (11), or, alternatively, as the difference between the productions achieved with

the partial extraction and with the complete extraction, equations (10) and (12), respectively:

$$(14) \quad \bar{X}_I^{G'} - \bar{X}_{I+VA}^{G'} = \{[v^1 \ v^R] - [\bar{v}^1 \ \bar{v}^R]\} \begin{bmatrix} (I - B^{11})^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & (I - B^{RR})^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$$

Table 7 shows schematically the equations that enable the calculation of the production of the production system, in the original state of equilibrium, and that reached when the partial extraction and the complete extraction occur.

Here, the HEM is developed and complemented with the extraction of a region, considering, firstly, the partial extraction of the input flow matrix and, secondly, the complete extraction of the input matrix and value added matrix, as shown in Table 7. These two extractions allow us to calculate the impact of the extraction of Region 1 from the value added matrix, which is a partial extraction.

Table 7. Level of production according to the different scenarios considered

Distribution coefficient matrix	Value added matrix	Equation to estimate the level of production	Ghosh model. Equilibrium production
$\begin{bmatrix} B^{11} & B^{1R} \\ B^{R1} & B^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} v^{11} & v^{1R} \\ v^{R1} & v^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$	$X' = [v^1 \ v^R] \begin{bmatrix} I - B^{11} & -B^{1R} \\ -B^{R1} & I - B^{RR} \end{bmatrix}^{-1}$	Original situation
$\begin{bmatrix} B^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & B^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} v^{11} & v^{1R} \\ v^{R1} & v^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$	$\bar{X}_{BI}^{G'} = [v^1 \ v^R] \begin{bmatrix} (I - B^{11})^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & (I - B^{RR})^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$	Partial extraction (I) Dietzenbacher et al.(1993a)
$\begin{bmatrix} B^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & B^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} v^{11} & 0 \\ 0 & v^{RR} \end{bmatrix}$	$\bar{X}_{BI+VA}^{G'} = [\bar{v}^1 \ \bar{v}^R] \begin{bmatrix} (I - B^{11})^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & (I - B^{RR})^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$	Complete extraction (I+VA)

Note: X' is the production level in the original situation; $\bar{X}_I^{G'}$ is the production level after extracting the intermediate goods flow matrix; $\bar{X}_{I+VA}^{G'}$ is the production level after extracting both the intermediate goods flow matrix and value added matrix.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

4. Empirical application to Spanish regions

4.1. Information sources. Database and processing

The EUREGIO database is a set of regional-sectoral input-output tables, at a global level, developed by the Tinbergen Institute (Thinssen et al., 2018) and is presented in a simplified form in Table A.1 of Annex A. In each of these input-output tables 266 economic areas are considered. The geographical breakdown covered by EUREGIO is outlined below:

- 249 administrative regions, or NUTS2, belonging to countries of the European Union are considered.
- 16 countries also participate that do not belong to the European Union; some are European and others not. Some of the countries that EUREGIO does not include in the European Union are, in fact, currently members of it⁸.
- A geographical area, referred to as “rest of the world”, encompasses information related to other countries included in the database.

Hereafter, the term region is used to refer to any of the geographic realities mentioned. Regarding Spain, the 17 CCAAs and the 2 Autonomous Cities of Ceuta and Melilla are considered, making a total of 19 Spanish regions which appear in the EUREGIO⁹. In the EUREGIO input-output table each region is broken down into 14 production sectors (see Annex A)¹⁰. The EUREGIO table is made up of three flow matrices: the input matrix in which the intersectoral relationships of the whole economic world are considered, $Z = [z_{ij}^{hk}]$; the final demand matrix¹¹ which considers the relationships between all the production sectors and the final sectors of each region, $F = [f_{ij}^{hm}]$; and, lastly, the value added matrix¹² which shows the elements of the value added generated in each of the sectors, $VA = [v_{k/j}(c)]$.

The equilibrium equations in the EUREGIO input-output table on the demand side are¹³:

$$(15) \quad X_i^h = \sum_{j=1}^{266} \sum_{k=1}^{14} z_{ij}^{hk} + \sum_{j=1}^{266} \sum_{m=1}^4 f_{ij}^{hm}$$

where: $(i = 1, 2, \dots, 266; h = 1, 2, \dots, 14; m = 1, \dots, 4)$

While the equilibrium relations on the supply side are:

⁸ The 16 countries are: Japan, Central and South America, Australia and Oceania, the United States, Mexico, Russia, Bulgaria, Romania, India, Indonesia, Cyprus, Canada, China, Korea, Turkey and Taiwan. Cyprus joined the European Union in 2004 and Romania and Bulgaria did so in 2007.

⁹ The 19 Spanish regions considered coincide with the Eurostat NUTS2 for Spain.

¹⁰ EUREGIO considers 14 sectors: 1) Primary, 2) Extractive industries, 3) Food, beverages and tobacco, 4) Textile, clothing, leather and footwear, 5) Coke and oil refining, rubber, chemical, metal products and others, 6) Electronic and optical equipment, vehicles and transport material, 7) Other manufacturing, 8) Construction, 9) Distribution, 10) Hotels and restaurants, 11) Transport, storage and communication, 12) Financial services and insurance, 13) Real estate activities and business services, and 14) Non-market services.

¹¹ There are 4 final demand sectors: private consumption, public consumption, gross capital formation and change in stocks.

¹² The components of value added are: wages, gross operating surplus, taxes and subsidies on products and the trade margin.

¹³ X_i^h is the total production of sector h of Region i.

$$(16) \quad X_j^k = \sum_{i=1}^{266} \sum_{h=1}^{14} z_{ij}^{hk} + \sum_{c=1}^4 v_{j/k}(c)$$

where: $(j = 1, 2, \dots, 266; k = 1, 2, \dots, 14; c = 1, \dots, 4)$

One of the advantages of this database is that it uses a homogeneous methodology for the different regions considered, which guarantees the comparability of the results between sectors, regions, and countries.

The statistical information in the input-output tables is collected in nominal terms and in billions of euros. There are eleven annual tables, one for each year of the period 2000-2010. In this study, to compare the estimates obtained through the two approaches considered - that of partial extraction and complete extraction - data from the input-output table of the year 2009 are used¹⁴.

Processing the information

The analysis carried out in this study requires an input-output table that enables the backward and forward effects of the Spanish regions to be determined with respect to themselves, the rest of the EU regions, and the rest of the world. To this end, an aggregation and disaggregation procedure is carried out in order to obtain a smaller input-output table, based on the EUREGIO table. The transformation process covers the following phases:

- First: the 14 production sectors of the input-output table of EUREGIO are added together; the 4 final demand sectors are consolidated into one and the 4 components of the value added of each of the regions are also consolidated into one. A global regional matrix of 266 regions is obtained.
- Second: The 266 regions are grouped into 21 groups, these being: the 17 Spanish CCAAs and the two autonomous cities of Ceuta and Melilla; a region that includes the rest of the EU regions considered in the database; and another region that brings together the information from the rest of the world economies also included in EUREGIO.
- Third: the value added of each region is broken down according to the production delivered to the other regions. This is a procedure of imputation of the value added to the regions that demand the goods of the region. The process is detailed below.

The unit value added vu_j is calculated for each region, $vu_j = \frac{v_j}{x_j}$; this gives the row vector of the unit value added vu . Also, the goods produced by each region are destined to be used as inputs or as final demand, so the matrix of total deliveries of goods, G , can be defined as:

¹⁴ The simulation exercise was carried out for the eleven years of the period 2000-2010 during which EUREGIO collated the database. However, for presentation reasons it was decided to show the results of only one year and the last year of the period was discarded since, as Prades and Tello (2020) detected, in the case of Catalonia and Andalusia, the commercial ties, both abroad and with other regions of Spain, seem to be underestimated. This is not so apparent in year 2009, so it was decided to show the results of this year.

$$(17) \quad G = Z + F$$

where $G = [g_{ij}] = [z_{ij}] + [f_{ij}]$ and z_{ij} is the value of the inputs, f_{ij} is the value of the final demand goods and, therefore, g_{ij} represents the total value of goods delivered to Region j by Region i.

Once the row vector of the unit value added vu and the delivery matrix G have been calculated, the matrix of imputed value added, V , can be calculated through the following equation:

$$(18) \quad V = G' \widehat{vu} = \begin{bmatrix} g_{1,1} vu_1 & \dots & g_{21,1} vu_{21} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ g_{1,21} vu_1 & \dots & g_{21,21} vu_{21} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v_1^1 & \dots & v_{21}^1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ v_1^{21} & \dots & v_{21}^{21} \end{bmatrix} = [v_j^i]$$

with \widehat{vu} being the diagonal matrix of the unit value added and v_j^i the value added generated by Region j due to all the goods delivered to Region i.

The result of the aggregation and disaggregation process is a symmetric input-output table (21x21) (see Table 2), which consists of:

1. An input matrix (21x21), $Z = [z_{ij}]$.
2. A final demand matrix (21x21), $F = [f_{ij}]$.
3. A row vector of aggregate value added (1x21), $v = [v_j]$.
4. An imputed value added matrix (21x21), $V = [v_j^i]$.
5. A vector of total production (21x1), $X = [X_i]$.

It must be emphasised, once again, that the square matrix of imputed value added has been estimated through the imputation of unit value added.

In order to validate the described procedure, once the V matrix has been obtained, the Leontief and Ghosh equations are used to verify that the aggregation and disaggregation procedures implemented keep the estimated regional total production of the CCAA unchanged. It is, in fact, verified that the estimated total production of each of the 17 Spanish CCAA calculated through equations (3), (9) and (19) is the same.

$$(19) \quad X' = e' V (I - B)^{-1}$$

Likewise, they coincide with the regional production given by EUREGIO, by means of equations (15) and (16), after sectoral aggregation.

4.2. Results analysis

The results from the HEM are presented using the *backward linkage* matrix, which Dietzenbacher et al (1993a) call matrix D. This matrix is presented in Table 8 and is used to interpret the results of the different extractions carried out.

Table 8. Backward linkage matrix

		Extracted Region i					
Affected Region j	R_1	...	R_i	...	R_j	...	R_{21}
R_1	$BE_1^1 = BE_1^R$...	BE_1^i	...	BE_1^j	...	BE_{21}^j
...
R_i	BE_i^1	...	$BE_i^i = BE_i^R$...	BE_i^j	...	BE_i^{21}
...
R_j	BE_j^1	...	BE_j^i	...	$BE_j^j = BE_j^R$...	BE_1^{21}
...
R_{21}	BE_{21}^1	...	BE_{21}^i	...	BE_{21}^j	...	$BE_{21}^{21} = BE_{21}^R$
Regional feedback	BE_1^1	...	BE_i^i	...	BE_j^j	...	BE_{21}^{21}
National BE	BE_N^1	...	BE_N^i	...	BE_N^j	...	BE_N^{21}
Exterior BE	BE_E^1	...	BE_E^i	...	BE_E^j	...	BE_E^{21}
Global BE	BE_G^1	...	BE_G^i	...	BE_G^j	...	BE_G^{21}
Backward or total impact	BE^1	...	BE^i	...	BE^j	...	BE^{21}
Production of extracted region	X_1	...	X_i	...	X_j	...	X_{21}

Note: BE= Backward effect y BE_i^R is the dependence of Region i when the rest of the regions are extracted.
 Source: Compiled by the authors.

In Table 8, the column corresponding to Region i reflects the effect in each of the regions when this region is extracted from the corresponding flow matrix. This decrease in output is due to the fact that it is a production linked to the manufacture of goods and/or services in Region i. It is a production that "is dependent", hence the term *backward dependence*. In particular, the elements BE_j^i of Table 8 indicate the backward dependence or the pull effect of the extracted Region i (dependent region) with respect to the affected Region j. In essence, this backward effect is the difference between the production of affected Region j before extraction, which is denoted as X_j , and production after extraction of Region i, denoted as \bar{X}_j^i :

$$(20) \quad BE_j^i = X_j - \bar{X}_j^i$$

In the analysis of interdependence between regions, it is often interesting to know what is called the net dependence of one region on another. In particular, the calculation of the net backward dependence between two regions can be calculate by comparing the backward effects that each region has on the other [see equation (20)], comparing BE_j^i and BE_i^j , such that if $BE_j^i > BE_i^j$ then Region i has net backward dependence with respect to Region j.

A measure of global backward dependence, BE_G^i , can be calculated for Region i with respect to the set of regions, by adding all regional backward dependence, as in the equation:

$$(21) \quad BE_G^i = \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^{21} BE_j^i = \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^{21} (X_j - \bar{X}_j^i)$$

In Table 8, the sum of the column corresponding to Region i, except for the element belonging to the main diagonal, provides the magnitude of the dependence of Region i with respect to the other regions, as shown in equation (21).

The global dependence or global backward effect can be decomposed into two components; one that reflects the pull on the regions of the same country, the *national backward effect*, BE_N^i (summation of BE_j^i for all the regions j of the same country), and another that reflects the pull on other countries, *external backward effect*, BE_E^i (summation of BE_j^i for j indicating the rest of the non-national regions of the EUREGIO database):

$$(22) \quad BE_G^i = BE_N^i + BE_E^i$$

In this way, the total impact on the production of Region i, BE^i , decomposes into three elements and can be determined by equation (23):

$$(23) \quad BE^i = BE_i^i + BE_N^i + BE_{Ex}^i$$

Note that element BE_i^i , in the main diagonal of Table 8, is the backward regional feedback. This indicates the production that Region i ceases to generate as it is isolated from the other regions. This is the production that Region i itself delivers to all other regions when it is integrated. This value is interpreted as the part of the production of Region i that the other regions need, which provides a measure of the aggregate backward dependence of the other regions with respect to this. In any case, we must not forget that $[BE_i^i = BE_i^R]$ is also a reduction of production in the economic system.

Analysing the information from the point of view of the affected region, the row corresponding to Region i of Table 8 reflects the decrease in its production as each of the other regions is successively isolated. Each of the values in the row, except the one belonging to the main diagonal, reflects the dependence (backward) of each region with respect to Region i.

Equations (20), (21), (22) and (23) quantify the backward dependence expressed in absolute terms. In line with Dietzenbacher et al. (1993a), this dependence can be expressed in relative terms, considering the original production level of the region extracted. Thus, the relative backward effect of the extracted Region i is the proportion of the backward effect (in absolute terms) with respect to the original production of that same region.

Similarly, the empirical results obtained using the HEM, following the Ghosh model, are collected in the so-called *forward linkage* matrix. Table 9 shows the different indicators that make up this matrix.

Table 9. Forward linkage matrix

		Extracted Region i					
Affected Region j	R_1	...	R_i	...	R_j	...	R_{21}
R_1	$FE_1^1 - FE_1^R$...	FE_1^i	...	FE_1^j	...	FE_1^{21}
...
R_i	FE_i^1	...	$FE_i^i - FE_i^R$...	FE_i^j	...	FE_i^{21}
...
R_j	FE_j^1	...	FE_j^i	...	$FE_j^j - FE_j^R$...	FE_j^{21}
...
R_{21}	FE_{21}^1	...	FE_{21}^i	...	FE_{21}^j	...	$FE_{21}^{21} - FE_{21}^R$
Regional feedback	FE_1^1	...	FE_i^i	...	FE_j^j	...	FE_{21}^{21}
National FE	FE_N^1	...	FE_N^i	...	FE_N^j	...	FE_N^{21}
Exterior FE	FE_E^1	...	FE_E^i	...	FE_E^j	...	FE_E^{21}
Global FE	FE_G^1	...	FE_G^i	...	FE_G^j	...	FE_G^{21}
Forward or total impact	FE^1	...	FE^i	...	FE^j	...	FE^{21}
Production of extracted region	X_1	...	X_i	...	X_j	...	X_{21}

Note: FE=forward effect y FE_i^R is the impulse effect of Region i when the rest of the regions are extracted.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

In a similar way to how the backward linkage matrix has been interpreted, the forward linkage matrix (Table 9) can be interpreted from the point of view of the extracted region (by columns) and from the point of view of the affected region (by rows). From the point of view of the extracted region, the column corresponding to Region i reflects the decrease in production of each one of the regions when this region is extracted from the corresponding flow matrix. By Region i ceasing to provide inputs to the others, the latter are forced to reduce their production. The receiving regions need the production of Region i for their production activity. The term *forward dependence* reflects the dependence of the isolated region on the regions as buyers of part of its production.

The forward dependence of the extracted region, Region i, with respect to another region, Region j, can be quantified through the forward effect or push effect, FE_j^i . This is

estimated as the difference between the production of the affected region, Region j, before extraction and after extraction of Region i, as shown in equation (24).

$$(24) \quad FE_j^i = X_j - \bar{X}_j^i$$

As in the case of backward dependence, the calculation of net forward dependence is useful when making comparisons between regions. This can be done easily by comparing FE_j^i and FE_i^j , the forward dependence of Region i with respect to Region j, and the forward dependence of Region j with respect to Region i, respectively. If $[FE_j^i > FE_i^j]$ then Region i is said to present a greater forward dependence with respect to Region j; or equivalently, that Region i has a net forward dependence on Region j.

A measure of global forward dependence, FE_G^i , can be calculated with respect to the set of other regions by adding all the regional forward dependence:

$$(25) \quad FE_G^i = \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^{21} (X_j - \bar{X}_j^i)$$

The global forward dependence of Region i provides a measure of the reduction of the production of the other regions in terms of buyers of its production¹⁵, as shown in equation (25).

At the aggregate level, the push effect can be decomposed into push in the regions of the same country, a national forward effect, FE_N^i , (summation of FE_j^i for all the regions j of the same country) and push in other countries, an exterior forward effect, FE_E^i (summation of FE_j^i for j indicating the rest of the non-national regions of the EUREGIO database:

$$(26) \quad FE_G^i = FE_N^i + FE_E^i$$

The total effect, FE^i , on the production is expressed by equation (27):

$$(27) \quad FE^i = FE_i^i + FE_N^i + FE_E^i$$

Element FE_i^i , in the main diagonal of Table 9, is the forward regional feedback that shows the production that the extracted region stops generating as it is isolated from the others. It can be considered as the personal production that is delivered to itself when it is integrated. Again, it must be remembered that $[FE_i^i = FE_i^R]$ is also a reduction in the production of the economic system.

From the point of view of the affected region, the i-th row of Table 9 reflects the decrease in the production of this region when each of the other regions is isolated separately. The values of the i-th row, FE_i^j , except for the one corresponding to the main diagonal, provide the forward dependence of each region with respect to Region i. These values can be

¹⁵ Alternative argument: being out of the flow matrix and no longer delivering goods reduces the production of the extracted region, which generates a reduction in production in the other regions.

interpreted as the dependence of each region j as a buyer of part of the production of Region i .

The forward dependence defined as in (27) is expressed in absolute terms. Similar to that of backward dependence, forward dependence can be quantified in relative terms, as the proportion with respect to the original production before extraction.

4.3. Empirical results

In order to compare the results obtained through the HEM approach proposed by Dietzenbacher et al. (1993a) and the one proposed in this paper each of the Spanish regions¹⁶ are extracted one by one from the input-output table of EUREGIO for the year 2009, after completing the aggregation explained previously. To obtain the level of production reached after the extraction of each of the regions by means of the partial extraction and/or complete extraction procedure, different ad-hoc scripts are programmed in the R Core Team software (2021) - versions 4.1.1 (2021-08-10) and 3.6.2 (2019-04-26).

Table 10 shows the general characteristics of the regions under study through different macroeconomic data. It is notable that the Community of Madrid ranks first in terms of production and demand for final goods. However, from the perspective of supply, through value added, this Community is relegated to second place in favour of Catalonia. Andalusia ranks third in terms of value added and fourth with regard to production, while the Valencian Community ranks fourth in value added and third in production.

Regarding the dependence results, the results of the backward dependence are shown first and then the results of the forward effects are shown. In both cases, the order of presentation of the results is, first, the partial extractions and then the complete extraction.

¹⁶ The autonomous cities of Ceuta and Melilla have also been extracted, and the economies configured for the rest of the EU NUTS2 and the rest of the countries included in EUREGIO, but the results are not included in the tables presented in this paper.

Table 10. Macroeconomic magnitudes and population for the year 2009

Name	Acronym	Intermediate demand	Final demand (FD)	Order according to FD	Intermediate consumption	Value added (VA)	Order according to VA	Production	Order according to production	Population	Order according to population
Andalusia	AND	47 116	127 148	3	39 083	135 181	3	174 264	4	8 213	1
Aragon	ARA	47 980	38 263	10	52 666	33 577	10	86 243	10	1 343	11
Asturias	AST	30 898	26 956	13	35 250	22 604	13	57 854	13	1 076	13
Balearic Islands	BAL	29 398	30 087	12	33 406	26 079	12	59 485	12	1 070	14
Canary Islands	CAN	44 930	46 249	8	50 774	40 405	8	91 179	9	2 025	9
Catalonia	CAT	76 206	154 512	2	47 142	183 576	1	230 718	2	7 427	2
Cantabria	CNT	16 627	14 679	16	18 606	12 700	16	31 306	16	585	16
Valencian Community	CV	118 487	106 625	4	124 695	100 417	4	225 112	3	4 981	4
Castile and Leon	CYL	72 996	66 448	6	84 693	54 752	7	139 444	7	2 549	6
Castile-La Mancha	CYM	49 658	45 806	9	57 570	37 894	9	95 464	8	2 066	8
Extremadura	EXT	21 401	21 497	14	25 991	16 908	15	42 898	15	1 095	12
Galicia	GAL	84 361	65 377	7	93 865	55 874	6	149 739	6	2 767	5
Community of Madrid	MAD	200 358	177 833	1	195 414	182 777	2	378 191	1	6 328	3
Region of Murcia	MUR	44 454	35 490	11	52 389	27 555	11	79 944	11	1 442	10
Navarre	NAV	26 515	20 228	15	28 976	17 767	14	46 742	14	627	15
The Basque Country	PV	101 468	71 223	5	108 643	64 048	5	172 691	5	2 174	7
Rioja	RIO	10 088	8 818	17	11 134	7 772	17	18 906	17	320	17

Note: The macroeconomic data are in billions of euros and the population in thousands of inhabitants.

Source: EUREGIO, INE and compiled by the authors.

In relation to backward dependence, in absolute value, Table 11 shows the effect of the extraction of each region on backward dependence, taking into account only the matrix of intermediate goods, obtained through equation (5). Table 12 shows the effect of the extraction of each region, considering only the matrix of final goods, obtained through equation (8). Finally, Table 13 shows the complete backward dependence, obtained through equation (7).

Overall, as can be seen in Tables 11 to 13, the smallest CCAAs in terms of volume of resources, such as Rioja, Navarre, Cantabria, and Extremadura, register the lowest backward effect, in absolute terms. On the contrary, the largest CCAAs, such as the Community of Madrid, Catalonia, Valencian Community, Andalusia, the Basque Country, and Galicia, present more intense effects.

However, when analysing the results for the three strategies considered, the inclusion or not of the final goods flow matrix is particularly important. To make comparisons between the results of the different extractions, the reference values provided by the HEM of Dietzenbacher et al. (1993c) are used.

The values for the three extractions considered, for the same extracted region, are significantly different and, furthermore, these values do not preserve the relative ordering in terms of having a greater or lesser effect on the extraction. As an example, let us consider the case of extraction of the region of Andalusia; partial extraction affecting only the input matrix provides a dependence of 733 billion euros with respect to Aragon (Table 11) and a regional feedback value of 30464. However, the partial extraction of that same region considering that it affects only the matrix of final goods, also for Aragon, provides a value of 1265 billion euros (Table 12), and a regional feedback value of 30580. In the case of complete extraction of Andalusia, the dependence on Aragon, as might be expected, becomes 1998 billion euros (Table 13), with regional feedback of 61044. Furthermore, analysing the order according to the impact on each of the extractions, it can be seen that, when extracting Andalusia, the Balearic Islands goes from being the 5th region with the lowest impact of partial extraction of only inputs to being the 15th region (4th with the greatest impact) if the extraction is partial of only final goods. Thus, the Balearic Islands becomes the 11th region with the least impact in the case of complete extraction. This shows that the effect on regional dependence varies, depending on the importance of the flows in final demand from one region to the others.

The impact of the effect of the partial extraction of only inputs with respect to the complete extraction, for example, when extracting Andalusia, indicates that the effect is multiplied by 3 in the case of Aragon, and even as much as 14 in the case of the Balearic Islands. If the effect between the regional feedback is compared, this is found to be double that of complete extraction.

All the above suggests that considering the extraction of a region as only affecting intermediate goods is masking the analysis and does not adequately measure the actual backward effect (complete) on the CCAAs. Thus, from the point of view of the regional backward effect, when a region is extracted only from the input matrix, the impact is significantly less than when it is jointly eliminated from the input flow and final demand matrices, being only 40% of the value shown by complete extraction. However, it should

be noted that the effect that occurs in the other regions when a specific region is extracted is not linear. This is seen, for example, when Andalusia is extracted since, while the impact in the Balearic Islands is 13.8 times greater in the complete extraction than in the partial extraction, for the Valencian Community the same impact is only 1.95 times greater in the complete extraction than in the partial one. Furthermore, the effect on the Balearic Islands of extracting Andalusia is, as already stated, 13.8 times greater in the complete extraction, while when extracting Madrid, it is only 1.32 times greater.

In summary, it should be noted that when analysing the results of the three perspectives considered, the significant importance of the final goods flow matrix is notable, such that the dependence on only intermediate goods could be biasing the full backward effect. If only the input flow matrix is considered when extracting a region, its effect is significantly less than if the input flow and final demand matrices are taken into account together.

When analysing the six most relevant CCAAs with respect to macroeconomic data, Graph 1 shows that the partial effects underestimate the backward effect. The backward effect in Madrid is higher than in the other CCAAs. In addition, the imbalance presented by the backward effect of inputs (BE total partial I) with respect to the backward effect of final demand (BE total partial FD) is apparent. Likewise, it is worth highlighting the fact that only in Andalusia the effect of the extraction of the final demand matrix is greater than that of the extraction of the input matrix (see Graph 1). Again, this fact shows that the dependence does not maintain the relative ordering in terms of greater or lesser affectation by the extraction.

Graph 1. Total backward dependence (billions of euros) of partial extractions (I and FD) and complete extraction (I + FD)

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Table 11. Backward linkages. Partial extraction (Input Matrix), 2009 (billions of euros)

Affected region	Extracted region																
	AND	ARA	AST	BAL	CAN	CNT	CYL	CYM	CAT	CV	EXT	GAL	MAD	MUR	NAV	PV	RIO
AND	30464	1005	639	783	1150	429	1599	1559	1101	2550	1424	1452	5462	2352	631	1748	330
ARA	733	25828	696	823	864	481	1560	1631	497	2750	1103	1353	6160	2385	857	1737	617
AST	205	507	13971	376	474	285	887	674	342	1281	519	658	2944	1081	375	1020	322
BAL	171	662	246	13179	546	257	475	580	237	1331	410	446	2883	1370	388	934	276
CAN	223	772	245	609	17461	337	544	711	224	1721	361	1105	3715	1027	503	1289	291
CNT	164	308	266	217	198	8858	478	461	88	717	474	331	2264	1053	265	659	269
CYL	815	1123	758	848	1313	547	30688	1635	760	3048	1048	1576	5833	2082	829	2103	618
CYM	810	960	549	631	862	470	1497	25487	415	2559	1089	1248	6325	2341	688	1607	516
CAT	1691	2544	1371	2244	2050	902	3157	2950	60693	5076	2383	3029	11826	4316	1365	3917	632
CV	2295	3067	1634	1821	2125	1114	4294	4055	2400	63789	2274	3643	13767	4919	1755	5140	1006
EXT	441	659	631	319	415	280	1343	1464	122	1288	14066	1088	2820	2009	368	696	380
GAL	1053	1495	949	1015	1464	650	2255	2065	890	3670	1250	37576	8294	2802	1027	2674	646
MAD	6588	6638	4473	4584	6635	2723	11431	10575	7383	16890	5129	11271	139762	9795	4057	15737	1880
MUR	1223	1662	664	1185	1278	596	2485	2624	861	4270	1702	2193	6096	29477	906	2013	545
NAV	412	666	419	463	408	327	947	876	195	1474	704	741	3598	1429	15098	1345	451
PV	2364	2567	1440	1621	1897	1045	4037	3378	1956	5684	2051	3478	12055	3896	2233	55444	956
RIO	153	380	144	195	156	188	462	379	83	608	454	279	1589	928	375	649	6814
Ceuta	153	18	14	23	15	22	15	16	11	19	18	15	125	25	14	37	22
Melilla	9	20	26	22	13	23	15	20	10	29	34	16	226	36	14	44	19
Rest of EU	13134	11536	6485	4663	7697	3216	14828	8916	20571	26008	5036	18447	62703	8931	5216	23242	1791
Rest of world	6278	6320	4946	3121	4812	2282	10263	6220	14924	17068	3313	11361	36581	5566	3405	15429	1369
Feedback regional	30464	25828	13971	13179	17461	8858	30688	25487	60693	63789	14066	37576	139762	29477	15098	55444	6814
National BE	19501	25053	15164	17778	21861	10677	37481	35653	17573	54967	22426	33919	95981	43845	16650	43347	9773
Exterior BE	19412	17856	11431	7783	12509	5498	25091	15135	35496	43077	8349	29809	99284	14496	8620	38671	3160
Total BE	69377	68737	40566	38741	51832	25032	93260	76275	113763	161833	44840	101304	335027	87819	40368	137462	19747

Note: BE= Backward effect, see Table 8.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Table 12. Backward linkages. Partial extraction (Final Demand Matrix), 2009 (billions of euros)

Affected region	Extracted region																
	AND	ARA	AST	BAL	CAN	CNT	CYL	CYM	CAT	CV	EXT	GAL	MAD	MUR	NAV	PV	RIO
AND	30580	922	797	982	918	575	1151	1177	2683	2188	2185	1107	1888	2590	694	1265	179
ARA	1265	18561	405	578	512	158	761	900	2211	1948	2169	625	1239	2441	414	417	332
AST	573	196	10324	245	181	156	434	360	1171	826	1331	222	840	1607	150	256	79
BAL	2197	482	89	14595	236	125	189	464	1769	1378	2038	409	938	2120	157	169	58
CAN	1409	651	546	701	23055	391	796	971	2106	2433	2087	1480	1649	3033	475	921	106
CNT	296	47	41	68	35	6613	256	157	846	608	1321	50	466	1337	64	118	43
CYL	1562	700	530	671	854	395	24171	1082	2347	1790	2110	930	2174	1739	479	975	276
CYM	1047	532	317	473	469	237	665	19814	2242	1837	2587	490	1738	2790	299	499	130
CAT	1999	1101	707	867	713	468	1334	1539	34373	2640	2902	1226	1696	3023	644	1269	163
CV	2203	1137	718	1045	1042	506	1420	1658	3656	33660	2462	1180	2921	3316	710	1279	287
EXT	871	340	278	217	139	87	489	599	1357	1072	8540	321	744	1094	113	197	101
GAL	1396	689	467	691	744	346	963	976	3193	2126	1942	24715	2303	2216	460	844	207
MAD	6748	1984	1780	2146	2299	1181	3261	3871	6352	6374	5109	3361	62013	5726	1469	3113	515
MUR	1386	559	227	725	501	164	723	984	2683	2444	1451	623	1166	14658	215	373	98
NAV	604	166	100	222	140	63	296	329	1192	977	1462	171	827	1607	9766	374	255
PV	2323	812	601	825	828	454	1426	1407	2995	2590	2267	1097	2110	2419	695	28184	409
RIO	232	92	30	55	29	24	75	113	577	454	899	40	308	732	132	151	4035
Ceuta	323	-2	-1	4	-1	0	-1	0	16	31	212	-1	1	159	-3	0	2
Melilla	9	18	90	12	3	55	5	29	76	30	213	6	6	10	6	5	10
Rest of EU	20275	5755	3492	3489	5911	2573	7205	6728	19977	14899	13302	7844	18553	14821	3327	6841	1530
Rest of world	9215	2758	1633	1648	2618	1350	3173	3066	8552	6677	7660	3487	8193	8430	1631	3062	803
Feedback regional	30580	18561	10324	14595	23055	6613	24171	19814	34373	33660	8540	24715	62013	5726	9766	28184	4035
National BE	26443	10427	7725	10525	9641	5386	14243	16615	37470	31747	34746	13338	23014	46895	7174	12225	3250
Exterior BE	29490	8513	5125	5137	8529	3923	10378	1658	28530	21577	20962	11331	26746	23250	4958	9903	2333
Total BE	86513	37501	23173	30256	41226	15921	48792	599	100373	86984	64248	49384	111772	75871	21897	50312	9618

Note: BE= Backward effect, see Table 8.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Table 13. Backward linkages. Complete extraction (Input + Final Demand Matrices), 2009 (billions of euros)

Affected region	Extracted region																
	AND	ARA	AST	BAL	CAN	CNT	CYL	CYM	CAT	CV	EXT	GAL	MAD	MUR	NAV	PV	RIO
AND	61044	1928	1437	1764	2068	1004	2750	2735	3783	4739	3609	2559	7350	4943	1324	3012	508
ARA	1998	44389	1101	1400	1376	639	2320	2530	2708	4699	3272	1978	7399	4826	1271	2155	949
AST	778	703	24295	621	655	441	1321	1033	1513	2107	1850	880	3785	2688	525	1276	401
BAL	2368	1143	335	27774	782	382	663	1044	2006	2709	2448	855	3821	3491	545	1103	333
CAN	1631	1423	792	1310	40517	727	1340	1682	2330	4153	2449	2585	5364	4060	978	2210	396
CNT	460	355	308	285	233	15470	734	618	934	1325	1795	381	2730	2389	329	777	312
CYL	2377	1823	1288	1519	2167	943	54859	2718	3107	4838	3158	2506	8006	3821	1308	3077	894
CYM	1857	1492	866	1104	1330	708	2162	45300	2657	4397	3676	1737	8063	5131	988	2106	646
CAT	3690	3646	2078	3111	2763	1370	4491	4489	95066	7716	5285	4254	13522	7339	2009	5185	795
CV	4497	4204	2353	2866	3167	1620	5714	5713	6056	97450	4735	4823	16688	8235	2465	6419	1293
EXT	1312	998	909	536	554	367	1831	2063	1478	2360	22606	1409	3564	3103	481	893	482
GAL	2449	2184	1416	1706	2208	996	3218	3042	4084	5795	3192	62291	10596	5018	1487	3519	853
MAD	13336	8622	6253	6731	8934	3904	14691	14446	13735	23265	10238	14631	201775	15522	5526	18850	2394
MUR	2609	2221	891	1909	1779	761	3209	3608	3544	6714	3152	2816	7262	44135	1121	2386	643
NAV	1016	832	519	685	548	390	1243	1204	1388	2452	2166	912	4424	3036	24863	1718	706
PV	4687	3379	2041	2446	2725	1499	5463	4785	4951	8274	4318	4575	14165	6315	2928	83628	1365
RIO	385	472	175	249	185	211	537	492	660	1063	1353	319	1897	1660	507	801	10849
Ceuta	476	16	12	27	14	22	15	16	27	51	230	14	126	184	11	36	23
Melilla	18	38	116	34	16	78	21	49	86	59	247	22	232	46	20	49	29
Rest of EU	33409	17291	9977	8152	13608	5789	22033	15644	40549	40908	18337	26291	81256	23751	8542	30082	3321
Rest of world	15493	9078	6579	4768	7430	3632	13437	9286	23477	23746	10973	14848	44774	13995	5036	18492	2172
Feedback regional	61044	44389	24295	27774	40517	15470	54859	45300	95066	97450	22606	62291	201775	44135	24863	83628	10849
National BE	45944	35480	22888	28303	31503	16062	51724	52268	55044	86715	57172	47257	118995	81808	23823	55572	13023
Exterior BE	48902	26369	16556	12920	21038	9421	35470	24929	64025	64653	29310	41140	126030	37747	13579	48574	5493
Total BE	155890	106238	63740	68997	93058	40953	142052	122498	214135	248817	109088	150687	446799	163690	62266	187774	29365

Note: BE= Backward effect, see Table 8.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Analysis of the backward effects in relative terms (see Tables B.1 to B.3 of Annex B), which are calculated considering the original production level of the extracted CCAAs, shows the dependence of the smaller CCAAs to be greater than that of the larger CCAAs. These results indicate that the smaller CCAAs present a greater dependence than the larger ones with respect to the consumption of inputs (see Table B.1 of Annex B). These results are in line with those obtained for the EU countries analysed by Dietzenbacher et al. (1993). Likewise, Table B.3 also corroborates a greater dependence of the smaller CCAAs, such that they are also highly dependent on the final demand of other CCAAs. These estimates highlight, as Llano (2004) already observed, that small regions with a high degree of trade openness are characterised by high dependence in relative terms.

Large regions, however, show high dependence or pull capacity in absolute terms, but lower in relative terms. According to the approach of Dietzenbacher et al. (1993a), the CCAAs with the lowest drag effect are Andalusia, Catalonia, Galicia, and the Valencian Community. However, the order with complete extraction would be Catalonia, Andalusia, Galicia, and the Basque Country. Once again, the results lead to different conclusions depending on the approach used. The conclusions are especially different when the focus is placed on the selection of the key regions of an economy since they are affected by the weight that each one of them has in the final demand. The greater the weight of final demand, the greater the underestimation of the region's pull capacity. Graph 1 highlights that the effect of final demand is very important; thus, for some regions their pull capacity will be undervalued if the matrix of final demand flows is not included in the HEM.

Backward regional feedback is seen to be the highest in the CCAA of Madrid, followed by the Valencian Community, Catalonia, and the Basque Country. In line with the data obtained by Llano (2009), these data, in relative terms, reflect that the dependence of the CCAA extracted from the other CCAAs is relatively low.

Tables 14 to 16 show dependence and forward regional feedback. Tables C.1, C.2 and C.3 of Annex C show the partial and complete push effects of extracting each Spanish CCAA from the corresponding flow matrices, in relative terms. Graph 2 includes, for each CCAA, the total forward dependence of the partial and complete extractions.

As indicated, excluding a community implies, according to Dietzenbacher (1993), that the supply of inputs from that community to the other CCAAs is extracted. As can be seen from Table 14, similar to backward dependence, the smaller CCAAs show smaller forward dependence, in absolute terms. In contrast, the largest CCAAs, such as Madrid, the Valencian Community, Catalonia, and the Basque Country present the highest push effects.

Regarding the complete extraction, Table 16 shows, in absolute terms, the push effects obtained. As can be seen, the effect of value added is significant, so that the full push effect is much higher than that obtained with the Dietzenbacher approach (1993). Likewise, the largest CCAAs show the biggest effects.

Graph 2 shows the partial and full forward effects, in absolute value, for the six largest CCAAs. The graph shows that in some CCAAs the push effect generated in the value added matrix is high, which suggests that not considering the effect of value added would lead to an underestimation of the push effect of the regions.

In relative terms (see Tables C.1, C.2 and C.3 of Annex C), as already observed with backward dependence, the highest forward effects correspond to the smallest CCAAs. This means that these CCAAs are more dependent on the rest of the CCAAs as buyers of their outputs. However, it is worth noting the high push effect presented by the Community of Madrid.

When comparing the two extraction approaches, it can again be seen that the CCAA ranking is different in the two approaches. In the first approach, the CCAAs with the greatest push effect, in relative terms, are the CCAAs of Rioja, Madrid, Region of Murcia and Extremadura. However, the ranking with the second approach is made up of the CCAAs of Extremadura, Region of Murcia, Rioja, and Madrid. Therefore, the order of the key regions is distorted depending on the approach used.

Graph 2. Total forward dependence (billions of euros) of the partial extractions of inputs (I) and of value added (VA) and of complete extraction (I + VA)

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Regional forward feedback is low in the smaller CCAAs, while Madrid, the Valencian Community and the Basque Country are, again, the CCAAs that present the greatest dependence on the other CCAAs. When the first approach is used for Catalonia, the low result is striking, given its size, indicating the limited relative dependence of this community on the consumption of its outputs by the other CCAAs. However, with the second approach, Catalonia presents a dependence similar to that of the Basque Country and the Valencian Community, which is more in line with its size.

5. Conclusions

The regional HEM, based on the hypothetical extraction of a region from an economic system, makes it possible to quantify the backward and forward dependence of the regions. It is a method accepted by the scientific community but, nevertheless, it is obvious that the hypothetical extraction of a region would affect not only the input flow matrix, as Dietzenbacher et al. (1993a) discuss, but also the final demand flow matrix and value added matrix. For this reason, this study proposes the inclusion in the hypothetical extraction of a region of the other two flow matrices of the economic system, which gives a more realistic and complete measure of both backward and forward dependence. When a region is hypothetically extracted, in order to infer its dependence on other regions, not only should the inputs it requires to produce be considered but also its dependence on final demand goods. Similarly, on the supply side, in the hypothetical extraction of a region not only should the push effect provided by the inputs the region delivers be taken into account but also that generated by the final goods it sells.

This study proposes a theoretical model that generalises the HEM, known as the complete extraction, both in the Leontief model and in the Ghosh model. The proposed procedure calls for three square matrices that collect the information on the input flows, final demand and value added. This study specifies the procedure for obtaining each one of them, especially that of imputed value added. First, the approach for the hypothetical partial and complete extraction of a region is explained in detail, both on the demand and supply side. The result of the theoretical development gives the equations necessary to quantify the incidence of the extraction of a region of any of the flow matrices. Next, and in order to verify the consequences of the inclusion of the other flow matrices, a simulation exercise is carried out, using the EUREGIO database for 2009. The results indicate that there are significant differences between the approach of Dietzenbacher et al. (1993a) and the one proposed. This means that the effects of partial and complete extraction could lead to different conclusions when quantifying the total volume of pull of a region. The same occurs with forward linkages, or push effect, when the flow of value added is included in the extraction. The results could also be biased when ranking the dependence of the regions.

The empirical results lead us to conclude that the smallest CCAAs are the most dependent because they depend on the inputs of the other CCAAs in order to produce outputs which are then purchased by these CCAAs.

Finally, it should be noted that the complete regional HEM proposed in this study could also be applied at the sectoral level in such a way that, instead of extracting the entire region, the effect of extracting a single sector from a region could be quantified. Likewise, it would be interesting to apply the methodology in the assumption of extracting a sector from all regions of the economic system. A practical application of the latter would be to see the global effect that the COVID-19 pandemic has had on the tourism sector.

Table 14. Forward linkages. Partial extraction (Input Matrix), 2009 (billions of euros)

Affected region	Extracted region																
	AND	ARA	AST	BAL	CAN	CNT	CYL	CYM	CAT	CV	EXT	GAL	MAD	MUR	NAV	PV	RIO
AND	21379	525	145	128	158	121	563	597	1739	1707	373	691	5473	967	298	1616	127
ARA	1405	33227	492	680	763	315	1082	986	3655	3188	775	1371	7710	1834	671	2450	437
AST	918	715	21056	260	247	280	751	578	2027	1748	765	894	5346	753	434	1413	170
BAL	1070	805	362	19348	591	222	801	635	3143	1848	371	910	5187	1278	459	1511	223
CAN	1619	869	464	565	26776	203	1275	892	2967	2226	492	1353	7766	1421	414	1824	180
CNT	582	466	271	258	323	11884	512	468	1255	1121	321	577	3060	638	321	966	211
CYL	2318	1616	895	507	557	510	49831	1598	4702	4629	1639	2147	13763	2846	991	3999	552
CYM	2116	1584	640	583	686	465	1532	37574	4110	4088	1675	1842	11902	2813	861	3131	428
CAT	1073	347	233	172	155	63	511	297	28712	1738	102	569	5970	663	138	1301	67
CV	3430	2644	1198	1316	1640	711	2827	2538	7013	73182	1459	3243	18866	4538	1432	5224	674
EXT	1693	939	431	360	304	417	860	954	2910	2010	20220	975	5064	1598	606	1665	446
GAL	2207	1470	696	499	1190	371	1652	1397	4730	4118	1393	53880	14230	2633	813	3612	349
MAD	6577	5304	2465	2552	3172	2015	4845	5621	14630	12326	2859	6567	133133	5802	3129	9925	1578
MUR	2973	2154	949	1272	917	980	1814	2180	5607	4624	2136	2325	10289	40761	1302	3365	965
NAV	872	847	361	395	491	268	790	699	1940	1806	428	931	4664	989	18948	2110	427
PV	2556	1816	1037	1005	1335	710	2121	1731	5884	5589	857	2569	19112	2325	1420	67255	782
RIO	397	532	270	244	246	237	514	457	785	904	387	510	1891	519	392	787	8248
Ceuta	101	34	21	18	15	21	32	43	105	77	32	36	192	45	26	57	19
Melilla	45	34	22	24	18	22	33	38	91	68	31	35	212	42	27	59	25
Rest of EU	12526	5604	3645	3121	4504	2221	8060	6304	25375	16577	2524	8522	33762	5201	3344	12006	1461
Rest of world	11071	5360	3158	3843	5463	1898	7744	6139	21317	14854	3191	8658	31191	5163	2924	10887	1282
Feedback regional	21379	33227	21056	19348	26776	11884	49831	37574	28712	73182	20220	53880	133133	40761	18948	67255	8248
National FE	31952	22702	10951	10839	12808	7931	22516	21709	67294	53816	16095	27545	140696	31704	13735	45016	7661
Exterior FE	23597	10965	6803	6964	9967	4119	15803	12443	46691	31431	5716	17180	64953	10364	6269	22894	2743
Total FE	76928	66894	38810	37150	49552	23934	88150	71726	142697	158429	42031	98605	338783	82829	38952	135166	18652

Note: FE= Forward effect, see Table 9.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Table 15. Forward linkages. Partial extraction (Value Added Matrix), 2009 (billions of euros)

Affected region	Extracted region																
	AND	ARA	AST	BAL	CAN	CNT	CYL	CYM	CAT	CV	EXT	GAL	MAD	MUR	NAV	PV	RIO
AND	47353	1325	1009	1240	1465	704	1883	1863	2631	3225	2527	1759	5080	3445	917	2088	325
ARA	846	17283	471	597	593	276	991	1070	1098	1945	1343	858	3014	1984	533	945	382
AST	372	331	9493	290	312	198	605	490	654	945	788	427	1588	1163	241	601	175
BAL	1106	563	186	12176	398	192	377	543	933	1324	1155	459	1834	1653	275	592	158
CAN	825	720	411	656	17954	363	721	875	1132	2044	1195	1276	2551	1954	489	1139	199
CNT	217	170	144	138	120	6276	336	287	405	591	767	192	1183	1033	151	365	133
CYL	1143	884	623	734	1015	445	21541	1327	1426	2286	1441	1235	3472	1801	620	1508	397
CYM	902	727	437	548	656	338	1071	17981	1217	2057	1626	889	3510	2297	476	1075	292
CAT	2250	2421	1346	2106	1779	876	2850	2837	75642	4872	3430	2729	9157	4747	1281	3386	442
CV	2063	1939	1096	1335	1478	749	2644	2638	2708	43470	2146	2258	7401	3718	1131	3012	573
EXT	588	459	405	266	279	173	822	910	646	1067	8911	649	1569	1363	231	464	206
GAL	1072	944	621	743	949	428	1402	1332	1663	2452	1328	23244	4148	2085	634	1553	347
MAD	6087	3931	2887	3083	4123	1775	6769	6629	6080	10577	4509	6794	97516	6884	2492	8872	1023
MUR	1082	924	415	788	757	333	1345	1475	1403	2680	1314	1190	2932	15213	489	1088	268
NAV	437	361	229	299	249	170	537	519	571	1022	884	409	1793	1244	9452	726	281
PV	1877	1363	834	996	1121	604	2201	1939	1927	3289	1704	1879	5256	2499	1152	31017	518
RIO	179	212	86	119	94	99	245	225	290	468	585	155	836	732	224	362	4461
Ceuta	245	9	6	15	8	11	10	10	15	30	120	9	72	98	6	21	11
Melilla	7	18	56	15	7	38	9	23	41	28	124	9	121	23	8	24	12
Rest of EU	16073	8210	4650	3652	6321	2648	10179	6881	19479	19166	8392	12508	39991	10659	3889	14306	1410
Rest of world	7374	4368	3152	2284	3538	1733	6369	4354	11135	11312	5244	7121	21679	6650	2380	8902	994
Feedback regional	47353	17283	9493	12176	17954	6276	21541	17981	75642	43470	8911	23244	97516	6884	9452	31017	4461
National FE	21298	17300	11261	13967	15400	7770	24816	24989	24840	40902	26985	23174	55517	47051	11348	27822	5741
Exterior FE	23447	12578	7802	5936	9858	4381	16548	2638	30614	30477	13636	19629	61670	17309	6268	23208	2403
Total FE	92098	47161	28555	32079	43213	18426	62904	910	131097	114849	49531	66047	214704	71244	27068	82047	12604

Note: FE= Forward effect, see Table 9.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Table 16. Forward linkages. Complete extraction (Input +Value Added Matrices), 2009 (billions of euros)

Affected region	Extracted region																
	AND	ARA	AST	BAL	CAN	CNT	CYL	CYM	CAT	CV	EXT	GAL	MAD	MUR	NAV	PV	RIO
AND	68732	1850	1154	1368	1623	824	2446	2460	4370	4932	2900	2450	10552	4412	1216	3704	452
ARA	2250	50510	963	1277	1356	591	2073	2056	4753	5133	2118	2229	10724	3819	1204	3395	819
AST	1290	1045	30548	550	559	479	1356	1068	2680	2693	1552	1321	6934	1916	675	2014	344
BAL	2176	1368	548	31524	989	413	1177	1178	4076	3171	1526	1370	7022	2931	734	2103	381
CAN	2444	1589	875	1221	44731	566	1995	1766	4100	4270	1687	2628	10317	3376	902	2963	378
CNT	799	637	415	396	443	18160	848	755	1660	1713	1089	769	4243	1671	472	1331	343
CYL	3461	2501	1518	1241	1572	955	71372	2926	6128	6915	3080	3381	17235	4647	1611	5507	950
CYM	3019	2311	1076	1131	1342	802	2603	55555	5327	6145	3301	2731	15412	5111	1337	4206	719
CAT	3322	2768	1579	2278	1934	939	3361	3134	104354	6610	3531	3298	15127	5410	1419	4687	509
CV	5493	4583	2294	2651	3118	1460	5471	5176	9721	116652	3605	5501	26267	8256	2563	8236	1247
EXT	2281	1398	836	626	583	590	1682	1864	3556	3077	29131	1624	6633	2962	837	2129	652
GAL	3279	2414	1317	1243	2139	799	3054	2728	6393	6570	2721	77123	18378	4718	1447	5166	697
MAD	12664	9234	5351	5635	7296	3790	11614	12249	20710	22903	7369	13361	230650	12686	5621	18796	2601
MUR	4055	3078	1363	2060	1674	1313	3158	3655	7009	7303	3450	3515	13220	55973	1791	4453	1233
NAV	1308	1207	590	693	741	438	1327	1218	2511	2828	1312	1340	6457	2233	28399	2836	708
PV	4433	3179	1871	2000	2456	1314	4322	3670	7811	8878	2561	4448	24368	4824	2572	98272	1300
RIO	576	744	356	364	340	336	759	682	1075	1373	971	665	2728	1250	616	1150	12709
Ceuta	347	44	27	33	23	32	41	54	120	107	152	45	264	142	32	77	30
Melilla	52	52	79	39	24	60	42	61	133	96	155	44	333	65	36	83	37
Rest of EU	28598	13814	8294	6773	10825	4869	18239	13185	44853	35743	10917	21031	73753	15860	7233	26312	2871
Rest of world	18446	9728	6311	6127	9001	3631	14112	10493	32452	26165	8435	15779	52870	11813	5304	19789	2275
Feedback regional	68732	50510	30548	31524	44731	18160	71372	55555	104354	116652	29131	77123	230650	55973	28399	98272	12709
National FE	53250	40002	22212	24805	28208	15701	47331	46698	92134	94717	43079	50719	196213	70427	25083	72838	13401
Exterior FE	47044	23542	14605	12900	19826	8500	32351	23678	77305	61909	19352	36809	126623	27673	12537	46102	5146
Total FE	169026	114054	67365	69229	92765	42360	151054	125930	273794	273278	91562	164652	553486	154074	66020	217212	31257

Note: FE= Forward effect, see Table 9.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

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Annex A. EUREGIO input-output table

As indicated, EUREGIO is a global symmetric input-output table with regional and sectoral breakdown that consists of:

- a) A matrix of intermediate goods or inputs: Z
- b) A matrix of final goods: F
- c) A vector of total productions: X
- d) A matrix of value added: VA

Table A.1. EUREGIO Input-Output matrix.

	R_1 $S_1 - S_{14}$	(R_j) $S_1 - S_{14}$	R_{266} $S_1 - S_{14}$	R_1 $F_1 - F_4$	(R_j) $F_1 - F_4$	R_{266} $F_1 - F_4$	X
R_1 $S_1 - S_{14}$	z_{ij}^{hk}			f_{ij}^{hm}			X_i^h
(R_i) $S_1 - S_{14}$							
R_{266} $S_1 - S_{14}$							
VA_1 VA_4	$v_{i/j}(c)$						
X'	X_j^k						

The subscripts refer to the region (R) of origin (i) and the region of destination (j) and the superscripts to the production sector (S) that delivers/sells (h) and the production sector that uses/buys (k). VA is the value added, X is the production and F the final demand.

h : Production sector¹⁷ [$h = 1, 2, \dots, 14$]

k : User sector [$k = 1, 2, \dots, 14$]

i : Region of production sector [$i = 1, 2, \dots, 266$] or region of origin.

¹⁷ Identified as sector producing the good.

j : Region of user sector [$j=1,2,\dots,266$] or region of destination.

- z_{ij}^{hk} Goods produced by sector h of Region i that are used as inputs in sector k of Region j .
- f_{ij}^{hm} Final goods produced by sector h of Region i that are purchased by final sector m of Region j , m being the sectors of final demand:
 $[m = 1, 2, 3, 4]$
1: Private expenditure
2: Public expenditure
3: Gross fixed capital formation
4: Change in stocks
- $v_{i/j}(c)$ Value added generated in the production sector of good k of Region j , with c being the different components of value added: $[c=1,2,3,4]$:
1: Wages
2: Gross production surplus
3: Taxes and subsidies on products
4: Trade margin
- X_i^h Total production of the sector producing the good h in Region i .

Such that:

- 1) $Z = [z_{ij}^{hk}]$ the square matrix $[(266 \times 14)(266 \times 14)]$ of inputs. Where z_{ij}^{hk} is the value of the inputs that sector h of Region i delivers to sector k of Region j .
- 2) $F = [f_{ij}^{hm}]$ the matrix $[(266 \times 14) \times 4]$ of final demand. Where f_{ij}^{hm} is the value of the goods that sector h of Region i delivers to the final sector m of Region j .
- 3) $VA = [v_{i/j}(c)]$ the matrix $[4 \times (266 \times 14)]$ of the value added of sector k of Region j . Where c is the value added component.
- 4) $X = [X_i^h]$ the column vector $[(266 \times 14) \times 1]$ of the total production of sector h of Region i .
- 5) $X' = [X_j^k]$ the row vector $[1 \times (266 \times 14)]$ of the total production of sector k of Region j .

Annex B. Backward linkages

Table B.1. Backward linkages. Partial extraction (Input), 2009 (%)

Affected region	Extracted region																
	AND	ARA	AST	BAL	CAN	CNT	CYL	CYM	CAT	CV	EXT	GAL	MAD	MUR	NAV	PV	RIO
AND	1,59%	1,17%	1,10%	1,32%	1,26%	1,37%	1,15%	1,63%	0,48%	1,13%	3,32%	0,97%	1,44%	2,94%	1,35%	1,01%	1,74%
ARA	0,42%	1,29%	1,20%	1,38%	0,95%	1,54%	1,12%	1,71%	0,22%	1,22%	2,57%	0,90%	1,63%	2,98%	1,83%	1,01%	3,26%
AST	0,12%	0,59%	0,69%	0,63%	0,52%	0,91%	0,64%	0,71%	0,15%	0,57%	1,21%	0,44%	0,78%	1,35%	0,80%	0,59%	1,70%
BAL	0,10%	0,77%	0,42%	0,65%	0,60%	0,82%	0,34%	0,61%	0,10%	0,59%	0,96%	0,30%	0,76%	1,71%	0,83%	0,54%	1,46%
CAN	0,13%	0,90%	0,42%	1,02%	0,88%	1,07%	0,39%	0,74%	0,10%	0,76%	0,84%	0,74%	0,98%	1,28%	1,08%	0,75%	1,54%
CNT	0,09%	0,36%	0,46%	0,37%	0,22%	0,43%	0,34%	0,48%	0,04%	0,32%	1,11%	0,22%	0,60%	1,32%	0,57%	0,38%	1,42%
CYL	0,47%	1,30%	1,31%	1,43%	1,44%	1,75%	1,58%	1,71%	0,33%	1,35%	2,44%	1,05%	1,54%	2,60%	1,77%	1,22%	3,27%
CYM	0,46%	1,11%	0,95%	1,06%	0,94%	1,50%	1,07%	1,28%	0,18%	1,14%	2,54%	0,83%	1,67%	2,93%	1,47%	0,93%	2,73%
CAT	0,97%	2,95%	2,37%	3,77%	2,25%	2,88%	2,26%	3,09%	3,27%	2,25%	5,55%	2,02%	3,13%	5,40%	2,92%	2,27%	3,34%
CV	1,32%	3,56%	2,82%	3,06%	2,33%	3,56%	3,08%	4,25%	1,04%	3,43%	5,30%	2,43%	3,64%	6,15%	3,76%	2,98%	5,32%
EXT	0,25%	0,76%	1,09%	0,54%	0,45%	0,89%	0,96%	1,53%	0,05%	0,57%	0,69%	0,73%	0,75%	2,51%	0,79%	0,40%	2,01%
GAL	0,60%	1,73%	1,64%	1,71%	1,61%	2,08%	1,62%	2,16%	0,39%	1,63%	2,91%	1,94%	2,19%	3,50%	2,20%	1,55%	3,42%
MAD	3,78%	7,70%	7,73%	7,71%	7,28%	8,70%	8,20%	11,08%	3,20%	7,50%	11,96%	7,53%	8,19%	12,25%	8,68%	9,11%	9,94%
MUR	0,70%	1,93%	1,15%	1,99%	1,40%	1,90%	1,78%	2,75%	0,37%	1,90%	3,97%	1,46%	1,61%	1,47%	1,94%	1,17%	2,88%
NAV	0,24%	0,77%	0,72%	0,78%	0,45%	1,04%	0,68%	0,92%	0,08%	0,65%	1,64%	0,49%	0,95%	1,79%	0,74%	0,78%	2,38%
PV	1,36%	2,98%	2,49%	2,73%	2,08%	3,34%	2,90%	3,54%	0,85%	2,52%	4,78%	2,32%	3,19%	4,87%	4,78%	2,90%	5,05%
RIO	0,09%	0,44%	0,25%	0,33%	0,17%	0,60%	0,33%	0,40%	0,04%	0,27%	1,06%	0,19%	0,42%	1,16%	0,80%	0,38%	0,33%
Ceuta	0,09%	0,02%	0,02%	0,04%	0,02%	0,07%	0,01%	0,02%	0,00%	0,01%	0,04%	0,01%	0,03%	0,03%	0,03%	0,02%	0,11%
Melilla	0,00%	0,02%	0,04%	0,04%	0,01%	0,07%	0,01%	0,02%	0,00%	0,01%	0,08%	0,01%	0,06%	0,04%	0,03%	0,03%	0,10%
Rest of EU	7,54%	13,38%	11,21%	7,84%	8,44%	10,27%	10,63%	9,34%	8,92%	11,55%	11,74%	12,32%	16,58%	11,17%	11,16%	13,46%	9,48%
Rest of world	3,60%	7,33%	8,55%	5,25%	5,28%	7,29%	7,36%	6,52%	6,47%	7,58%	7,72%	7,59%	9,67%	6,96%	7,28%	8,93%	7,24%
Feedback regional	1,59%	1,29%	0,69%	0,65%	0,88%	0,43%	1,58%	1,28%	3,27%	3,43%	0,69%	1,94%	8,19%	1,47%	0,74%	2,90%	0,33%
National BE	11,19%	29,05%	26,21%	29,89%	23,98%	34,10%	26,88%	37,35%	7,62%	24,42%	52,28%	22,65%	25,38%	54,85%	35,62%	25,10%	51,69%
Exterior BE	11,14%	20,70%	19,76%	13,08%	13,72%	17,56%	17,99%	15,85%	15,38%	19,14%	19,46%	19,91%	26,25%	18,13%	18,44%	22,39%	16,72%
Total BE	22,33%	49,75%	45,97%	42,97%	37,70%	51,66%	44,87%	53,20%	23,00%	43,55%	71,74%	42,56%	51,63%	72,98%	54,06%	47,49%	68,41%

Note: BE= Backward effect, see Table 8.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Table B.2. Backward linkages. Partial extraction (Final Demand), 2009 (%)

Affected region	Extracted region																
	AND	ARA	AST	BAL	CAN	CNT	CYL	CYM	CAT	CV	EXT	GAL	MAD	MUR	NAV	PV	RIO
AND	1,60%	1,07%	1,38%	1,65%	1,01%	1,84%	0,83%	1,23%	1,16%	0,97%	5,09%	0,74%	0,50%	3,24%	1,48%	0,73%	0,95%
ARA	0,73%	0,93%	0,70%	0,97%	0,56%	0,50%	0,55%	0,94%	0,96%	0,87%	5,06%	0,42%	0,33%	3,05%	0,89%	0,24%	1,76%
AST	0,33%	0,23%	0,51%	0,41%	0,20%	0,50%	0,31%	0,38%	0,51%	0,37%	3,10%	0,15%	0,22%	2,01%	0,32%	0,15%	0,42%
BAL	1,26%	0,56%	0,15%	0,72%	0,26%	0,40%	0,14%	0,49%	0,77%	0,61%	4,75%	0,27%	0,25%	2,65%	0,34%	0,10%	0,30%
CAN	0,81%	0,75%	0,94%	1,18%	1,16%	1,25%	0,57%	1,02%	0,91%	1,08%	4,87%	0,99%	0,44%	3,79%	1,02%	0,53%	0,56%
CNT	0,17%	0,05%	0,07%	0,11%	0,04%	0,32%	0,18%	0,16%	0,37%	0,27%	3,08%	0,03%	0,12%	1,67%	0,14%	0,07%	0,23%
CYL	0,90%	0,81%	0,92%	1,13%	0,94%	1,26%	1,24%	1,13%	1,02%	0,80%	4,92%	0,62%	0,57%	2,18%	1,03%	0,56%	1,46%
CYM	0,60%	0,62%	0,55%	0,79%	0,51%	0,76%	0,48%	1,00%	0,97%	0,82%	6,03%	0,33%	0,46%	3,49%	0,64%	0,29%	0,69%
CAT	1,15%	1,28%	1,22%	1,46%	0,78%	1,49%	0,96%	1,61%	1,85%	1,17%	6,76%	0,82%	0,45%	3,78%	1,38%	0,73%	0,86%
CV	1,26%	1,32%	1,24%	1,76%	1,14%	1,62%	1,02%	1,74%	1,58%	1,81%	5,74%	0,79%	0,77%	4,15%	1,52%	0,74%	1,52%
EXT	0,50%	0,39%	0,48%	0,37%	0,15%	0,28%	0,35%	0,63%	0,59%	0,48%	0,42%	0,21%	0,20%	1,37%	0,24%	0,11%	0,54%
GAL	0,80%	0,80%	0,81%	1,16%	0,82%	1,10%	0,69%	1,02%	1,38%	0,94%	4,53%	1,28%	0,61%	2,77%	0,98%	0,49%	1,10%
MAD	3,87%	2,30%	3,08%	3,61%	2,52%	3,77%	2,34%	4,06%	2,75%	2,83%	11,91%	2,24%	3,63%	7,16%	3,14%	1,80%	2,72%
MUR	0,80%	0,65%	0,39%	1,22%	0,55%	0,52%	0,52%	1,03%	1,16%	1,09%	3,38%	0,42%	0,31%	0,73%	0,46%	0,22%	0,52%
NAV	0,35%	0,19%	0,17%	0,37%	0,15%	0,20%	0,21%	0,34%	0,52%	0,43%	3,41%	0,11%	0,22%	2,01%	0,48%	0,22%	1,35%
PV	1,33%	0,94%	1,04%	1,39%	0,91%	1,45%	1,02%	1,47%	1,30%	1,15%	5,29%	0,73%	0,56%	3,03%	1,49%	1,47%	2,16%
RIO	0,13%	0,11%	0,05%	0,09%	0,03%	0,08%	0,05%	0,12%	0,25%	0,20%	2,10%	0,03%	0,08%	0,92%	0,28%	0,09%	0,20%
Ceuta	0,19%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,01%	0,49%	0,00%	0,00%	0,20%	-0,01%	0,00%	0,01%
Melilla	0,01%	0,02%	0,16%	0,02%	0,00%	0,18%	0,00%	0,03%	0,03%	0,01%	0,50%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	0,01%	0,00%	0,05%
Rest of EU	11,63%	6,67%	6,04%	5,87%	6,48%	8,22%	5,17%	7,05%	8,66%	6,62%	31,01%	5,24%	4,91%	18,54%	7,12%	3,96%	8,09%
Rest of world	5,29%	3,20%	2,82%	2,77%	2,87%	4,31%	2,28%	3,21%	3,71%	2,97%	17,86%	2,33%	2,17%	10,54%	3,49%	1,77%	4,25%
Feedback regional	1,60%	0,93%	0,51%	0,72%	1,16%	0,32%	1,24%	1,00%	1,85%	1,81%	0,42%	1,28%	3,63%	7,16%	0,48%	1,47%	0,20%
National BE	15,17%	12,09%	13,35%	17,69%	10,57%	17,20%	10,21%	17,40%	16,24%	14,10%	81,00%	8,91%	6,09%	41,05%	15,35%	7,08%	17,19%
Exterior BE	16,92%	9,87%	8,86%	8,64%	9,35%	12,53%	7,44%	10,26%	12,37%	9,58%	48,86%	7,57%	7,07%	29,08%	10,61%	5,73%	12,34%
Total BE	33,70%	22,89%	22,72%	27,05%	21,08%	30,06%	18,90%	28,66%	30,46%	25,50%	130,28%	17,75%	16,79%	77,30%	26,43%	14,29%	29,72%

Note: BE= Backward effect, see Table 8.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Table B.3. Backward linkages. Complete extraction (Input + Final Demand), 2009 (%)

Affected region	Extracted region																
	AND	ARA	AST	BAL	CAN	CNT	CYL	CYM	CAT	CV	EXT	GAL	MAD	MUR	NAV	PV	RIO
AND	3,19%	2,24%	2,48%	2,97%	2,27%	3,21%	1,97%	2,87%	1,64%	2,11%	8,41%	1,71%	1,94%	6,18%	2,83%	1,74%	2,69%
ARA	1,15%	2,22%	1,90%	2,35%	1,51%	2,04%	1,66%	2,65%	1,17%	2,09%	7,63%	1,32%	1,96%	6,04%	2,72%	1,25%	5,02%
AST	0,45%	0,82%	1,20%	1,04%	0,72%	1,41%	0,95%	1,08%	0,66%	0,94%	4,31%	0,59%	1,00%	3,36%	1,12%	0,74%	2,12%
BAL	1,36%	1,33%	0,58%	1,37%	0,86%	1,22%	0,48%	1,09%	0,87%	1,20%	5,71%	0,57%	1,01%	4,37%	1,17%	0,64%	1,76%
CAN	0,94%	1,65%	1,37%	2,20%	2,03%	2,32%	0,96%	1,76%	1,01%	1,85%	5,71%	1,73%	1,42%	5,08%	2,09%	1,28%	2,10%
CNT	0,26%	0,41%	0,53%	0,48%	0,26%	0,75%	0,53%	0,65%	0,40%	0,59%	4,18%	0,25%	0,72%	2,99%	0,70%	0,45%	1,65%
CYL	1,36%	2,11%	2,23%	2,55%	2,38%	3,01%	2,82%	2,85%	1,35%	2,15%	7,36%	1,67%	2,12%	4,78%	2,80%	1,78%	4,73%
CYM	1,07%	1,73%	1,50%	1,86%	1,46%	2,26%	1,55%	2,28%	1,15%	1,95%	8,57%	1,16%	2,13%	6,42%	2,11%	1,22%	3,42%
CAT	2,12%	4,23%	3,59%	5,23%	3,03%	4,38%	3,22%	4,70%	5,13%	3,43%	12,32%	2,84%	3,58%	9,18%	4,30%	3,00%	4,21%
CV	2,58%	4,87%	4,07%	4,82%	3,47%	5,18%	4,10%	5,98%	2,62%	5,24%	11,04%	3,22%	4,41%	10,30%	5,27%	3,72%	6,84%
EXT	0,75%	1,16%	1,57%	0,90%	0,61%	1,17%	1,31%	2,16%	0,64%	1,05%	1,11%	0,94%	0,94%	3,88%	1,03%	0,52%	2,55%
GAL	1,41%	2,53%	2,45%	2,87%	2,42%	3,18%	2,31%	3,19%	1,77%	2,57%	7,44%	3,22%	2,80%	6,28%	3,18%	2,04%	4,51%
MAD	7,65%	10,00%	10,81%	11,31%	9,80%	12,47%	10,54%	15,13%	5,95%	10,33%	23,87%	9,77%	11,82%	19,42%	11,82%	10,92%	12,66%
MUR	1,50%	2,58%	1,54%	3,21%	1,95%	2,43%	2,30%	3,78%	1,54%	2,98%	7,35%	1,88%	1,92%	2,20%	2,40%	1,38%	3,40%
NAV	0,58%	0,97%	0,90%	1,15%	0,60%	1,25%	0,89%	1,26%	0,60%	1,09%	5,05%	0,61%	1,17%	3,80%	1,22%	0,99%	3,73%
PV	2,69%	3,92%	3,53%	4,11%	2,99%	4,79%	3,92%	5,01%	2,15%	3,68%	10,07%	3,06%	3,75%	7,90%	6,26%	4,37%	7,22%
RIO	0,22%	0,55%	0,30%	0,42%	0,20%	0,67%	0,39%	0,52%	0,29%	0,47%	3,15%	0,21%	0,50%	2,08%	1,09%	0,46%	0,52%
Ceuta	0,27%	0,02%	0,02%	0,05%	0,02%	0,07%	0,01%	0,02%	0,01%	0,02%	0,54%	0,01%	0,03%	0,23%	0,02%	0,02%	0,12%
Melilla	0,01%	0,04%	0,20%	0,06%	0,02%	0,25%	0,01%	0,05%	0,04%	0,03%	0,57%	0,01%	0,06%	0,06%	0,04%	0,03%	0,15%
Rest of EU	19,17%	20,05%	17,25%	13,70%	14,92%	18,49%	15,80%	16,39%	17,57%	18,17%	42,75%	17,56%	21,49%	29,71%	18,28%	17,42%	17,57%
Rest of world	8,89%	10,53%	11,37%	8,02%	8,15%	11,60%	9,64%	9,73%	10,18%	10,55%	25,58%	9,92%	11,84%	17,51%	10,77%	10,71%	11,49%
Feedback regional	3,19%	2,22%	1,20%	1,37%	2,03%	0,75%	2,82%	2,28%	5,13%	5,24%	1,11%	3,22%	11,82%	2,20%	1,22%	4,37%	0,52%
National BE	26,36%	41,14%	39,56%	47,58%	34,55%	51,31%	37,09%	54,75%	23,86%	38,52%	133,27%	31,56%	31,46%	102,33%	50,97%	32,18%	68,88%
Exterior BE	28,06%	30,58%	28,62%	21,72%	23,07%	30,09%	25,44%	26,11%	27,75%	28,72%	68,32%	27,47%	33,32%	47,22%	29,05%	28,13%	29,05%
Total BE	54,43%	71,71%	68,18%	69,30%	57,62%	81,40%	62,53%	80,87%	51,61%	67,24%	201,60%	59,03%	64,79%	149,55%	80,02%	60,31%	97,93%

Note: BE= Backward effect, see Table 8.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Annex C. Forward linkages

Table C.1. Forward linkages. Partial extraction (Input), 2009 (%)

Affected region	Extracted region																
	AND	ARA	AST	BAL	CAN	CNT	CYL	CYM	CAT	CV	EXT	GAL	MAD	MUR	NAV	PV	RIO
AND	1,12%	0,61%	0,25%	0,22%	0,17%	0,39%	0,40%	0,63%	0,75%	0,76%	0,87%	0,46%	1,45%	1,21%	0,64%	0,94%	0,67%
ARA	0,81%	1,66%	0,85%	1,14%	0,84%	1,01%	0,78%	1,03%	1,58%	1,42%	1,81%	0,92%	2,04%	2,29%	1,44%	1,42%	2,31%
AST	0,53%	0,83%	1,04%	0,44%	0,27%	0,89%	0,54%	0,61%	0,88%	0,78%	1,78%	0,60%	1,41%	0,94%	0,93%	0,82%	0,90%
BAL	0,61%	0,93%	0,63%	0,95%	0,65%	0,71%	0,57%	0,67%	1,36%	0,82%	0,86%	0,61%	1,37%	1,60%	0,98%	0,87%	1,18%
CAN	0,93%	1,01%	0,80%	0,95%	1,34%	0,65%	0,91%	0,93%	1,29%	0,99%	1,15%	0,90%	2,05%	1,78%	0,89%	1,06%	0,95%
CNT	0,33%	0,54%	0,47%	0,43%	0,35%	0,58%	0,37%	0,49%	0,54%	0,50%	0,75%	0,39%	0,81%	0,80%	0,69%	0,56%	1,12%
CYL	1,33%	1,87%	1,55%	0,85%	0,61%	1,63%	2,56%	1,67%	2,04%	2,06%	3,82%	1,43%	3,64%	3,56%	2,12%	2,32%	2,92%
CYM	1,21%	1,84%	1,11%	0,98%	0,75%	1,48%	1,10%	1,89%	1,78%	1,82%	3,90%	1,23%	3,15%	3,52%	1,84%	1,81%	2,26%
CAT	0,62%	0,40%	0,40%	0,29%	0,17%	0,20%	0,37%	0,31%	1,55%	0,77%	0,24%	0,38%	1,58%	0,83%	0,30%	0,75%	0,36%
CV	1,97%	3,07%	2,07%	2,21%	1,80%	2,27%	2,03%	2,66%	3,04%	3,93%	3,40%	2,17%	4,99%	5,68%	3,06%	3,03%	3,57%
EXT	0,97%	1,09%	0,75%	0,61%	0,33%	1,33%	0,62%	1,00%	1,26%	0,89%	0,99%	0,65%	1,34%	2,00%	1,30%	0,96%	2,36%
GAL	1,27%	1,70%	1,20%	0,84%	1,31%	1,18%	1,18%	1,46%	2,05%	1,83%	3,25%	2,78%	3,76%	3,29%	1,74%	2,09%	1,85%
MAD	3,77%	6,15%	4,26%	4,29%	3,48%	6,44%	3,47%	5,89%	6,34%	5,48%	6,67%	4,39%	7,80%	7,26%	6,69%	5,75%	8,35%
MUR	1,71%	2,50%	1,64%	2,14%	1,01%	3,13%	1,30%	2,28%	2,43%	2,05%	4,98%	1,55%	2,72%	2,03%	2,79%	1,95%	5,10%
NAV	0,50%	0,98%	0,62%	0,66%	0,54%	0,86%	0,57%	0,73%	0,84%	0,80%	1,00%	0,62%	1,23%	1,24%	0,93%	1,22%	2,26%
PV	1,47%	2,11%	1,79%	1,69%	1,46%	2,27%	1,52%	1,81%	2,55%	2,48%	2,00%	1,72%	5,05%	2,91%	3,04%	3,52%	4,14%
RIO	0,23%	0,62%	0,47%	0,41%	0,27%	0,76%	0,37%	0,48%	0,34%	0,40%	0,90%	0,34%	0,50%	0,65%	0,84%	0,46%	0,40%
Ceuta	0,06%	0,04%	0,04%	0,03%	0,02%	0,07%	0,02%	0,05%	0,05%	0,03%	0,07%	0,02%	0,05%	0,06%	0,06%	0,03%	0,10%
Melilla	0,03%	0,04%	0,04%	0,04%	0,02%	0,07%	0,02%	0,04%	0,04%	0,03%	0,07%	0,02%	0,06%	0,05%	0,06%	0,03%	0,13%
Rest of EU	7,19%	6,50%	6,30%	5,25%	4,94%	7,09%	5,78%	6,60%	11,00%	7,36%	5,88%	5,69%	8,93%	6,51%	7,15%	6,95%	7,73%
Rest of world	6,35%	6,22%	5,46%	6,46%	5,99%	6,06%	5,55%	6,43%	9,24%	6,60%	7,44%	5,78%	8,25%	6,46%	6,26%	6,30%	6,78%
Feedback regional	1,12%	1,66%	1,04%	0,95%	1,34%	0,58%	2,56%	1,89%	1,55%	3,93%	0,99%	2,78%	7,80%	2,03%	0,93%	3,52%	0,40%
National FE	18,34%	26,32%	18,93%	18,22%	14,05%	25,33%	16,15%	22,74%	29,17%	23,91%	37,52%	18,40%	37,20%	39,66%	29,39%	26,07%	40,52%
Exterior FE	13,54%	12,71%	11,76%	11,71%	10,93%	13,16%	11,33%	13,03%	20,24%	13,96%	13,32%	11,47%	17,17%	12,96%	13,41%	13,26%	14,51%
Total FE	31,88%	39,04%	30,69%	29,93%	24,98%	38,49%	27,48%	35,77%	49,40%	37,87%	50,84%	29,87%	54,38%	52,62%	42,80%	39,32%	55,03%

Note: FE= Forward effect, see Table 9.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Table C.2. Forward linkages. Partial extraction (Value Added), 2009 (%)

Affected region	Extracted region																
	AND	ARA	AST	BAL	CAN	CNT	CYL	CYM	CAT	CV	EXT	GAL	MAD	MUR	NAV	PV	RIO
AND	2,48%	1,54%	1,74%	2,08%	1,61%	2,25%	1,35%	1,95%	1,14%	1,43%	5,89%	1,17%	1,34%	4,31%	1,96%	1,21%	1,72%
ARA	0,49%	0,86%	0,81%	1,00%	0,65%	0,88%	0,71%	1,12%	0,48%	0,86%	3,13%	0,57%	0,80%	2,48%	1,14%	0,55%	2,02%
AST	0,21%	0,38%	0,47%	0,49%	0,34%	0,63%	0,43%	0,51%	0,28%	0,42%	1,84%	0,28%	0,42%	1,45%	0,52%	0,35%	0,92%
BAL	0,63%	0,65%	0,32%	0,60%	0,44%	0,61%	0,27%	0,57%	0,40%	0,59%	2,69%	0,31%	0,49%	2,07%	0,59%	0,34%	0,84%
CAN	0,47%	0,83%	0,71%	1,10%	0,90%	1,16%	0,52%	0,92%	0,49%	0,91%	2,79%	0,85%	0,67%	2,44%	1,05%	0,66%	1,05%
CNT	0,12%	0,20%	0,25%	0,23%	0,13%	0,31%	0,24%	0,30%	0,18%	0,26%	1,79%	0,13%	0,31%	1,29%	0,32%	0,21%	0,70%
CYL	0,66%	1,03%	1,08%	1,23%	1,11%	1,42%	1,11%	1,39%	0,62%	1,02%	3,36%	0,82%	0,92%	2,25%	1,33%	0,87%	2,10%
CYM	0,52%	0,84%	0,75%	0,92%	0,72%	1,08%	0,77%	0,90%	0,53%	0,91%	3,79%	0,59%	0,93%	2,87%	1,02%	0,62%	1,54%
CAT	1,29%	2,81%	2,33%	3,54%	1,95%	2,80%	2,04%	2,97%	4,08%	2,16%	8,00%	1,82%	2,42%	5,94%	2,74%	1,96%	2,34%
CV	1,18%	2,25%	1,89%	2,24%	1,62%	2,39%	1,90%	2,76%	1,17%	2,34%	5,00%	1,51%	1,96%	4,65%	2,42%	1,74%	3,03%
EXT	0,34%	0,53%	0,70%	0,45%	0,31%	0,55%	0,59%	0,95%	0,28%	0,47%	0,44%	0,43%	0,41%	1,71%	0,49%	0,27%	1,09%
GAL	0,62%	1,09%	1,07%	1,25%	1,04%	1,37%	1,01%	1,40%	0,72%	1,09%	3,09%	1,20%	1,10%	2,61%	1,36%	0,90%	1,84%
MAD	3,49%	4,56%	4,99%	5,18%	4,52%	5,67%	4,85%	6,94%	2,64%	4,70%	10,51%	4,54%	5,71%	8,61%	5,33%	5,14%	5,41%
MUR	0,62%	1,07%	0,72%	1,32%	0,83%	1,06%	0,96%	1,54%	0,61%	1,19%	3,06%	0,79%	0,78%	0,76%	1,05%	0,63%	1,42%
NAV	0,25%	0,42%	0,40%	0,50%	0,27%	0,54%	0,39%	0,54%	0,25%	0,45%	2,06%	0,27%	0,47%	1,56%	0,46%	0,42%	1,49%
PV	1,08%	1,58%	1,44%	1,67%	1,23%	1,93%	1,58%	2,03%	0,84%	1,46%	3,97%	1,26%	1,39%	3,13%	2,47%	1,62%	2,74%
RIO	0,10%	0,25%	0,15%	0,20%	0,10%	0,32%	0,18%	0,24%	0,13%	0,21%	1,36%	0,10%	0,22%	0,92%	0,48%	0,21%	0,22%
Ceuta	0,14%	0,01%	0,01%	0,02%	0,01%	0,03%	0,01%	0,01%	0,01%	0,01%	0,28%	0,01%	0,02%	0,12%	0,01%	0,01%	0,06%
Melilla	0,00%	0,02%	0,10%	0,03%	0,01%	0,12%	0,01%	0,02%	0,02%	0,01%	0,29%	0,01%	0,03%	0,03%	0,02%	0,01%	0,06%
Rest of EU	9,22%	9,52%	8,04%	6,14%	6,93%	8,46%	7,30%	7,21%	8,44%	8,51%	19,56%	8,35%	10,57%	13,33%	8,32%	8,28%	7,46%
Rest of world	4,23%	5,06%	5,45%	3,84%	3,88%	5,53%	4,57%	4,56%	4,83%	5,02%	12,22%	4,76%	5,73%	8,32%	5,09%	5,15%	5,25%
Feedback regional	2,48%	0,86%	0,47%	0,60%	0,90%	0,31%	1,11%	0,90%	4,08%	2,34%	0,44%	1,20%	5,71%	8,61%	0,46%	1,62%	0,22%
National FE	12,22%	20,06%	19,46%	23,48%	16,89%	24,82%	17,80%	26,18%	10,77%	18,17%	62,90%	15,48%	14,68%	40,58%	24,28%	16,11%	30,36%
Exterior FE	13,45%	14,58%	13,49%	9,98%	10,81%	13,99%	11,87%	2,76%	13,27%	13,54%	31,79%	13,11%	16,31%	21,65%	13,41%	13,44%	12,71%
Total FE	28,15%	35,51%	33,42%	34,06%	28,60%	39,12%	30,77%	0,95%	28,11%	34,04%	95,13%	29,79%	36,70%	70,85%	38,15%	31,17%	43,29%

Note: FE= Forward effect, see Table 9.

Source. Compiled by the authors.

Table C.3. Forward linkages. Complete extraction (Input + Value Added), 2009 (%)

Affected region	Extracted region																
	AND	ARA	AST	BAL	CAN	CNT	CYL	CYM	CAT	CV	EXT	GAL	MAD	MUR	NAV	PV	RIO
AND	3,60%	2,15%	1,99%	2,30%	1,78%	2,63%	1,75%	2,58%	1,89%	2,19%	6,76%	1,64%	2,79%	5,52%	2,60%	2,14%	2,39%
ARA	1,29%	2,53%	1,67%	2,15%	1,49%	1,89%	1,49%	2,15%	2,06%	2,28%	4,94%	1,49%	2,84%	4,78%	2,58%	1,97%	4,33%
AST	0,74%	1,21%	1,51%	0,92%	0,61%	1,53%	0,97%	1,12%	1,16%	1,20%	3,62%	0,88%	1,83%	2,40%	1,44%	1,17%	1,82%
BAL	1,25%	1,59%	0,95%	1,56%	1,08%	1,32%	0,84%	1,23%	1,77%	1,41%	3,56%	0,91%	1,86%	3,67%	1,57%	1,22%	2,02%
CAN	1,40%	1,84%	1,51%	2,05%	2,24%	1,81%	1,43%	1,85%	1,78%	1,90%	3,93%	1,76%	2,73%	4,22%	1,93%	1,72%	2,00%
CNT	0,46%	0,74%	0,72%	0,67%	0,49%	0,88%	0,61%	0,79%	0,72%	0,76%	2,54%	0,51%	1,12%	2,09%	1,01%	0,77%	1,82%
CYL	1,99%	2,90%	2,62%	2,09%	1,72%	3,05%	3,67%	3,06%	2,66%	3,07%	7,18%	2,26%	4,56%	5,81%	3,45%	3,19%	5,02%
CYM	1,73%	2,68%	1,86%	1,90%	1,47%	2,56%	1,87%	2,79%	2,31%	2,73%	7,69%	1,82%	4,08%	6,39%	2,86%	2,44%	3,80%
CAT	1,91%	3,21%	2,73%	3,83%	2,12%	3,00%	2,41%	3,28%	5,63%	2,94%	8,23%	2,20%	4,00%	6,77%	3,04%	2,71%	2,69%
CV	3,15%	5,31%	3,96%	4,46%	3,42%	4,66%	3,92%	5,42%	4,21%	6,27%	8,40%	3,67%	6,95%	10,33%	5,48%	4,77%	6,60%
EXT	1,31%	1,62%	1,45%	1,05%	0,64%	1,88%	1,21%	1,95%	1,54%	1,37%	1,43%	1,08%	1,75%	3,70%	1,79%	1,23%	3,45%
GAL	1,88%	2,80%	2,28%	2,09%	2,35%	2,55%	2,19%	2,86%	2,77%	2,92%	6,34%	3,98%	4,86%	5,90%	3,10%	2,99%	3,68%
MAD	7,27%	10,71%	9,25%	9,47%	8,00%	12,11%	8,33%	12,83%	8,98%	10,17%	17,18%	8,92%	13,51%	15,87%	12,03%	10,88%	13,76%
MUR	2,33%	3,57%	2,36%	3,46%	1,84%	4,19%	2,27%	3,83%	3,04%	3,24%	8,04%	2,35%	3,50%	2,79%	3,83%	2,58%	6,52%
NAV	0,75%	1,40%	1,02%	1,17%	0,81%	1,40%	0,95%	1,28%	1,09%	1,26%	3,06%	0,89%	1,71%	2,79%	1,39%	1,64%	3,74%
PV	2,54%	3,69%	3,23%	3,36%	2,69%	4,20%	3,10%	3,84%	3,39%	3,94%	5,97%	2,97%	6,44%	6,03%	5,50%	5,14%	6,88%
RIO	0,33%	0,86%	0,61%	0,61%	0,37%	1,07%	0,54%	0,71%	0,47%	0,61%	2,26%	0,44%	0,72%	1,56%	1,32%	0,67%	0,61%
Ceuta	0,20%	0,05%	0,05%	0,06%	0,03%	0,10%	0,03%	0,06%	0,05%	0,05%	0,35%	0,03%	0,07%	0,18%	0,07%	0,04%	0,16%
Melilla	0,03%	0,06%	0,14%	0,07%	0,03%	0,19%	0,03%	0,06%	0,06%	0,04%	0,36%	0,03%	0,09%	0,08%	0,08%	0,05%	0,20%
Rest of EU	16,41%	16,02%	14,34%	11,39%	11,87%	15,55%	13,08%	13,81%	19,44%	15,88%	25,45%	14,04%	19,50%	19,84%	15,47%	15,24%	15,19%
Rest of world	10,58%	11,28%	10,91%	10,30%	9,87%	11,60%	10,12%	10,99%	14,07%	11,62%	19,66%	10,54%	13,98%	14,78%	11,35%	11,46%	12,03%
Feedback regional	3,60%	2,53%	1,51%	1,56%	2,24%	0,88%	3,67%	2,79%	5,63%	6,27%	1,43%	3,98%	13,51%	2,79%	1,39%	5,14%	0,61%
National FE	30,56%	46,38%	38,39%	41,70%	30,94%	50,15%	33,94%	48,92%	39,93%	42,08%	100,42%	33,87%	51,88%	88,10%	53,66%	42,18%	70,88%
Exterior FE	27,00%	27,30%	25,24%	21,69%	21,74%	27,15%	23,20%	24,80%	33,51%	27,50%	45,11%	24,58%	33,48%	34,62%	26,82%	26,70%	27,22%
Total FE	57,55%	73,68%	63,64%	63,39%	52,68%	77,30%	57,14%	73,72%	73,44%	69,58%	145,53%	58,45%	85,36%	122,71%	80,48%	68,87%	98,10%

Note: FE= Forward effect, see Table 9.

Source: Compiled by the authors.